

Protocol on the characterization of the FOODLAND novel raw materials, ingredients, and food products

D5.15

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Main author(s):	Nchimbi Msolla S., Suleiman R. (SUA); Essaidi I., Hamrouni M., Ben Abdsslem S., Dhief A., Khalifa B. (ISACM); Jribi S., Ghanem R., Ben Souissi J., Rjiba W., Khamassi F. (INAT); Muyonga J.H. (MAK); Girmay G. (UoM); Okoth M.W., Ngala S., Kaindi D.W.M. (UoN); Masette M., Tinyro S.E., Akullo D., Fred W., Cassius A. (NARO); Bajoub A. (ENAM); Nakimbugwe D. (NUT); Tappi S., Valli E., Tura M., Garcia Salas P., Gallina Toschi T. (UNIBO)		
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Short Description	
<p>This deliverable includes the description of the analytical methods (procedures, techniques, tools, target properties) that have been, are and will be used in the relevant project Food Hubs for the characterization of the new raw materials, ingredients, food products developed by FoodLAND. In particular, the aim is to determine the composition, functional and sensory properties and nutritional characteristics of the realized products.</p>	
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Table of Contents

Table of Contents	1
1. Organization of the work	3
1.1. Describing and sharing the analytical methods of characterization	3
2. Description of the analytical methods used in the relevant project Food Hubs for the characterization of the new raw materials, ingredients, food products	4
2.1. SUA	6
2.1.1. Raw materials: novel improved legume lines (<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> L.) (prototype n. 7a, 7b, 8)	6
2.1.2. Composite flours with novel local varieties: white maize, millet, bio-fortified common beans, soybeans, and sesame seeds (prototype n. 11c)	11
2.2. ISACM	16
2.2.1. Composite flours with novel local varieties: wheat; legumes (pea, faba bean, chickpea) (prototype n. 11a)	16
2.2.2. Composite flours with novel local varieties: vegetables composite flours (leaf: parsley, spinach, chard; bulb: potato, carrot; spice: tomato, onion) (prototype n. 11b)	16
2.2.3. Snacks from novel local varieties / species (cookies): wheat; legumes (pea / faba bean / chickpea) (prototype n. 21a)	37
2.2.4. Snacks from novel local varieties / species (energetic bars): wheat flasks; dried fruits (apricot, peach, melon) (prototype n. 21b)	45
2.3. INAT	51
2.3.1. Composite flours with novel local varieties: composite flour (prototype n. 11b)	51
2.3.2. Dried products: dried fish (prototype n. 15b), dried vegetables (prototype n. 15c)	54
2.4. MAK	66
2.4.1. Composite flours with novel local varieties: orange fleshed sweet potatoes, grain amaranth, amaranth-enriched wheat, and pumpkin (prototype n. 12)	66
2.4.2. Snacks from novel local varieties/species: orange fleshed sweet potatoes, grain amaranth, and pumpkin (prototype n. 20)	81
2.5. UoM	84
2.5.1. Composite flours with novel local varieties: moringa and teff (prototype n. 13)	84
2.6. UoN	90
2.6.1. Composite flours with novel local varieties: therapeutic powder for diabetic people (prototype n. 14)	90

2.6.2. Therapeutic food: tamarillo juice for adults with diabetes (prototype n. 24).....	92
2.6.3. Snacks from novel local varieties/species: cereal-based snacks for children (prototype n. 23)	96
2.7. NARO	100
2.7.1. Dried products: dried fish (prototype n. 15a), fish powder (prototype n. 16) ..	100
2.7.2. Oils from novel local varieties/species: fish oil (prototype n. 18)	102
2.7.3. Snacks from novel local varieties/species: fish cakes and crackers (prototype n. 22)	103
2.7.4. Other products from novel local varieties/species: other fish products (prototype n. 25a)	103
2.8. ENAM	106
2.8.1. Oils from novel local varieties/species: virgin and/or extra virgin olive oil (prototype n. 17)	106
2.9. NUT	114
2.9.1. Other products: bean sauce (prototype n. 25b)	114
2.9.2. Other products: amaranth-enriched wheat (prototype n. 25c)	116
3. Determination of Acrylamide in Food Products	119
3.1 Purpose	119
3.2 Principle	119
3.3 Materials, Apparatus and Equipment	119
3.4 Procedures	119
4. Determination of Mycotoxins in Cereal-Based Products	121
4.1 Purpose	121
4.2 Principle	121
4.3 Materials, Apparatus and Equipment	121
4.4 Procedures	122

1. Organization of the work

1.1. Describing and sharing the analytical methods of characterization

The objectives of Task 5.6 are to carry out the characterization of the new raw materials, ingredients and food products realized by the project, to validate their compositions, acceptability and, ultimately, their capacity to ensure balanced and healthy diets.

To achieve these objectives, a series of online meetings with relevant partners and ad hoc sessions at the in person general meetings have been organized. During these meetings, FoodLAND partners presented the analytical procedures for characterizing their new products under development, shared their experiences and procedures, discussed and solved issues or criticalities, and presented the first achieved results (reported in D4.13).

In operative terms, UNIBO created shared folders in the project repository (Figure 1.1.1) and invited all partners to upload and share the analytical methods and the results of the characterization activities according to the project template (Figure 1.1.2).

The screenshot shows a SharePoint document library interface for 'FoodLAND Gruppo privato'. The breadcrumb path is 'Documenti > Working Groups > Characterization and Labelling'. The table below lists the shared folders:

Nome	Data/ora modif...	Modificato da	+ Aggiungi colonna
ENAM (MA)	18 giugno 2021	Enrico Valli	
INAT (TN)	18 giugno 2021	Enrico Valli	
ISA-CM (TN)	16 luglio 2021	Celeste Lazzarini - celeste.	
MAK (UG)	16 luglio 2021	Celeste Lazzarini - celeste.	
NARO (UG)	16 luglio 2021	Celeste Lazzarini - celeste.	
SUA (TZ)	16 luglio 2021	Celeste Lazzarini - celeste.	
Templates	Pochi secondi fa	Celeste Lazzarini - celeste.	
UoM (ET)	16 luglio 2021	Celeste Lazzarini - celeste.	
UoN (KE)	16 luglio 2021	Celeste Lazzarini - celeste.	

Figure 1.1.1. Shared folders created for each partner

 ANALYTICAL METHOD

Determination of **in**
Depending on the type of analysis, please fill in the sections that you consider as relevant

- 1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address**
- 2. Purpose**
A brief description of the purpose of the SOP (Standard Operation Procedure), it should describe the aim of the analysis.
- 3. Principle**
A general introduction with the principles behind the method, with a statement of rationale.
- 4. Definitions and abbreviations**
A list of definitions can be included for terms used in the SOP.
- 5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment**
List and specify where necessary under each of the headings
 - 5.1 Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials**
 - 5.2 Equipment, instruments**
 - 5.3 Health and Safety and personal Protective Equipment (PPE)**
Indicate what could happen if the procedure is not followed correctly
- 5. Procedures**
A detailed description of the steps and procedures to be performed. There should be sufficient details, clearly expressed, to enable a trained person to perform the procedure without supervision. There should also be sufficient details to enable a trained person to use the document to train others to perform the task.
 - 6.1 Sample preparation**
 - 6.2 Analysis**
 - 6.3 Schematic of method**

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 ANALYTICAL METHOD

The use of a flow diagram can be useful, especially in complex procedures.

6.4 Instrumentation: analytical conditions

7. Control procedures
Describe the preparation of the appropriate quality-control procedures (self-checks, calibrations), quality-control material (blanks, spikes, replicates) that are required to demonstrate successful performance of the method. Describe frequency of required control checks, the limits/criteria for the data/results, actions required when quality-control data exceeds the limits and procedures for reporting quality-control data.

8. Calculations and data analysis
Describe how to calculate and express the results. Results will be discussed in the related document to report results.

9. References
Cite any relevant bibliographic references, sufficient for the user to find the source document (please also include web references where possible).

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Figure 1.1.2. Template for the description of the analytical methods

2. Description of the analytical methods used in the relevant project Food Hubs for the characterization of the new raw materials, ingredients, food products

Herein, a description of the analytical methods that have been, are and will be used in the relevant project Food Hubs for the characterization of the new raw materials, ingredients, food products developed by FoodLAND is provided. The aim is to determine the composition, functional, nutritional and sensory properties and nutritional characteristics of the 24 new realized products.

Table 1.2.1. New project food raw materials, ingredients, and products.

(Prototype n.) New project foods	Partner
Raw materials	
(7a, 7b, 8) <u>Improved legume lines</u> (<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> L.)	SUA
Ingredients	
(11.-14.) <u>Composite flours with novel local varieties</u> (<i>vegetables, legumes, cereals</i>) (ST4.4.2) 11.a wheat; legumes (<i>pea, faba bean, chickpea</i>) 11.b vegetables composite flours (<i>leaf: parsley, spinach, chard; bulb: potato, carrot; spice: tomato, onion</i>) 11.c composite flour (<i>white maize, millet, bio-fortified common beans, soybeans, and sesame seeds</i>) 11.d composite flour (<i>cereals, legumes and vegetables flour</i>) 12. orange fleshed sweet potatoes, grain amaranth, and pumpkin (<i>wheat flour; bio-fortified beans, orange fleshed sweet potatoes</i>) 13. moringa and teff 14. therapeutic powder for diabetic people (<i>tree tomato</i>) (ST4.5.2)	ISACM ISACM SUA INAT MAK UoM UoN
15. <u>Dried products</u> 15.a dried fish (salted, smoked, fermented) from new aquaculture species (<i>Barbus altianalis / Labeo victorianus</i>) (<i>dried, salted and smoked Tilapia, Catfish and Barbus; fermentation for by-products, production of feed</i>) 15.b dried fish (<i>mullet, tilapia and eel, bottarga</i>) 15.c dried vegetables (<i>tomato, peppers, strawberries, eggplant, aromatic plants: onion, garlic</i>)	NARO INAT INAT
16. <u>Fish powders</u>	NARO
Food products	
(17.-19.) <u>Oils from novel local varieties / species</u> 17. virgin and/or extra virgin olive oil 18. fish oils	ENAM NARO

19. moringa oil (<i>not to be developed</i>)	UoM
(20.-23.) <u>Snacks from novel local varieties / species</u> (ST4.5.3)	
20. orange fleshed sweet potatoes and grain amaranth (<i>wheat flour, bio-fortified beans, orange fleshed sweet potatoes-noodles, bakery products</i>)	MAK
21.a cookies: wheat; legumes (<i>pea / faba bean / chickpea</i>)	ISACM
21.b energetic bars: wheat flasks; dried fruits (<i>apricot, peach, melon</i>)	ISACM
22. fish cakes and crackers	NARO
23. cereal-based snack for children (<i>quinoa snack for children</i>)	UoN
24. <u>Therapeutic food</u> (<i>tamarillo juice, for adults with diabetes</i>)	UoN
25. <u>Other products</u>	
25.a Fish fillets, balls, noodles, nuggets, sausages, and burgers	NARO
25.b Bean sauce	NUT
25.c Amaranth-enriched wheat	NUT

The specific parameters selected for the characterization were chosen for each raw material/ingredient/food product based on its specific properties, stability and nutritional value and on the aim of the new product development (e.g., shelf-life enhancement, nutritional value improvement, product diversification etc). Moreover, the specific partner analytical ability was taken into account, evaluating the possibility for out-sourcing some analytical determinations.

2.1. SUA

2.1.1. Raw materials: novel improved legume lines (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) (prototype n. 7a, 7b, 8)

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Rashid Suleiman and Prof. Susan Nchimbi-Msolla, Sokoine University of Agriculture (SUA):
rashid@sua.ac.tz; nchimbi@sua.ac.tz

2. Product

A novel improved legume line (*Phaseolus vulgaris L.*) is a new type of common bean with improved micronutrients. The bean was obtained from the Mvomero Food Hub. The improved varieties of beans have higher micronutrients, especially iron and zinc, to improve their nutritional composition.

3. Method of analysis

The beans were washed to remove dust, stones, sand, and any other impurities, and then dried for 4 hours at 50°C before milling into flour. After milling, it was analysed for physico-chemical properties, proximate analysis, minerals, and vitamins. For physico-chemical analysis, the parameters analysed were bulk density, angle of repose, water absorption and water solubility indices, and oil absorption index. For proximate analysis, parameters include moisture contents, ash, crude protein, and fats. The minerals analysed were iron, zinc, copper, magnesium, calcium, manganese, potassium, and sodium. Also, vitamin A and total phenol were analysed.

Determination of Bulk density

Bulk density was measured according to Hasmadi (2021) with slight modification.

The flour sample was filled to a known volume in a measuring cylinder. The volume was then read directly from the cylinder and corresponding mass was recorded from analytical balance. The bulk density was calculated according to the relationship:

$$\text{Bulk density} = \text{Mass/volume (g/cm}^3\text{)}.$$

Angle of Repose

Angle of Repose was determined by Fixed Funnel Method as explained by Brian (2018). Flour material was poured through a funnel to form a cone. The tip of the funnel should be held close to the growing cone and slowly raised as the pile grows, to minimize the impact of falling particles. Stop pouring the material when the pile reaches a predetermined height or the base a predetermined width. Then Angle of Repose is given by the equation

$$\tan^{-1}(2h/r)$$

where **h**-is height of the pile from the base to the tip and **r** is radius of pile.

Water Absorption and Water Solubility Indices

Water absorption and Water solubility indices was determined by method outlined by Nargis Yousef et al. (2017). Water absorption index (WAI) measures the volume occupied by the granule or starch polymer after swelling in excess of water. The flour samples (0.2g) were suspended in distilled water (5mL) at room temperature for 30 minutes, gently stirred during this period and then centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes. The supernatant liquid was poured carefully in to

tared evaporating dish. The remaining gel was weighed and WAI was calculated as grams of gel obtained per gram of solid;

$$\text{WAI} = M_g / M_s$$

Where M_g is the weight of the hydrated gel (g) and M_s is the weight of sample (g)

Water solubility index (WSI) determines the amount of polysaccharides release from the granule on the addition of excess of water. WSI was the weight of dry solids in the supernatant from the water absorption index test above expressed as percentage of the original weight of the sample. Water solubility index (WSI) was determined from the amount of dry solids recovered by evaporating the supernatant from the water absorption test as;

$$\text{WSI (\%)} = \text{Weight of dissolved solid in supernatant} / \text{Weight of dry solids} * 100$$

Oil Absorption Index

Oil Absorption Index (OAI) was determined according to the method of Liadakis et al. (1993), refined sunflower oil (6mL) was added to sample (1.0 gm) in a graduated centrifuge tube. The tube was agitated for 1min, left for 30 min and centrifuge for 20 min at 3000 rpm; the volume of the free oil was read. OAI was calculated as:

$$\text{OAI} = \text{Voil} / M$$

Where Voil is the volume of oil absorbed (mL) and M is the weight of the sample (g).

Proximate analysis

-Determination of moisture content (AOAC, 1990)

Moisture content was determined by oven drying method, about 5g of well-mixed sample was accurately weighed in clean, dry Petri-dish. The Petri-dish was dried in an oven at 105°C for 24 hours until a constant weight was obtained. Then, the Petri-dish was placed in the desiccator for 30 minutes to cool. After cooling, it was weighed again. The percent moisture (%) was calculated by the following formula:

$$\% \text{ Moisture content} = \frac{\text{Moisture Weight}}{\text{Weight of sample (g)}} \times 100$$

-Determination of ash content (AOAC, 1990)

For the determination of ash, a clean empty crucible and lid was placed in a muffle furnace at 550°C for one hour to ensure that all possible impurities on the surface of crucible were burned off. They were then cooled in desiccator for 30 minutes and then weight of empty crucible and their lids was noted W1. About 5g of sample was taken in crucible (W2). The sample was heated over Bunsen flame with lid half covered. When fumes were no longer produced, the crucible and

lid were placed in furnace. The crucibles with their content were heated overnight. After complete heating, the lid covered the crucible to prevent loss of fluffy ash. The sample in crucible was cooled down in the desiccator. The weight of the ash with crucible and the lid was determined.

$$\% \text{ Ash content} = \frac{\text{Weight of Ash(g)}}{\text{weight of sample(g)}} \times 100$$

-Determination of crude protein (AOAC, 2000)

Protein sample was determined by Kjeldahl method, as described in AOAC (2000). According to this method, samples were digested by heating with concentrated sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄) in the presence of Kjeldahl catalyst. The mixture was then made alkaline and distilled into a boric acid solution. The borate ions formed was titrated against standard sulphuric acid 0.05N, which is converted to total nitrogen in the sample, then multiplied by 6.25 conversion factor to crude protein.

-Determination of fat content (AOAC, 2000)

Total fat was determined by using Soxhlet ether extraction official method 922.06 (AOAC, 2000). Five (5) g of flour sample were placed into the extraction thimble and assembled to the Soxhlet apparatus. The petroleum ether 70 mL were used for continuous reflux for 55 min in three phases, the boiling phase for 15 min, the rinsing phase for 30 min and petroleum ether recovery phase for 10 min. The remaining Petroleum ether was then evaporated. Pre-weighed cups containing fat were dried in an oven at 105°C for 1 h to evaporate any remaining petroleum ether, cooled in a desiccator for 30 min and weighed. Percentage fat was calculated by using the formula:

$$\% \text{ Fat Content} = \frac{\text{Weight of crude fat(g)}}{\text{Weight of samples(g)}}$$

Micronutrients analysis

-Vitamin A (β-Carotene)

Beta carotene determination was done according to Delia and Mieko (2004), with slightly modifications, where 2.0g homogenized sample taken into Polytron bottle was extracted by using 50mLs of cold acetone. Then the portions of extracts were transferred into the separating funnel contained 25 mL of petroleum ether (40-60°C Bp) for partitioning, followed by washing with about 125 mL of distilled water until the extracts were acetone free. The washed samples were then passed through anhydrous sodium sulphate to make it free from any trace of water. The dried carotene extracts were then collected into a clean and dry volumetric flask. The extract was then read under UV-Visible Spectrophotometer at 450nm (Double beam UV-3000 model X-ma3000 spectrophotometer Human Corporation, England).

Beta carotene standard solution with the concentration of 110mg/mL was prepared by taking 0.0110g of β -carotene standard powder obtained from Sigma-Adrich into 100mL volumetric flask. 10mL petroleum ether added and swirled to dissolve and finely petroleum ether added until the volume made to 100mL mark of the volumetric flask. Serial dilution of 0mg/mL, 0.1mg/mL, 0.2mg/mL, 0.4mg/mL and 0.6mg/mL were prepared by taking 0mL, 0.2mL, 0.4mL, 0.8mL and 1.0mL of the stock standard solution (110mg/mL) into 25mL volumetric flask. Petroleum ether added to complete volumes (25mL).

Absorbencies of the diluted standards read, and standard calibration plot constructed the linear regression equation obtained which will be used to calculate the Beta-carotene content of the samples (Rasaki, 2009).

-Minerals

One (1.0) g of homogenized sample weighed into clean pre-treated porcelain crucible. Incinerated into muffle furnace at 450°C for four hours. The obtained ashes of the sample are then dissolved with 10mL of 6% Hydrochloric acid solution, filtered using No. 1 Whatman filter papers and diluted to 100mL with distilled water. The filtrates are then read in Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (UNICAM 919 AAS, England) for Iron and Zinc at 248.3nm and 219.81nm respectively (AOAC 1999 Meth. No. 999.10A).

4. Control procedures

All analytical determinations were carried out in duplicate to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

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2.1.2. Composite flours with novel local varieties: white maize, millet, bio-fortified common beans, soybeans, and sesame seeds (prototype n. 11c)

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Rashid Suleiman, Sokoine University of Agriculture (SUA): rashid@sua.ac.tz

2. Product

Composite flour

3. Method of analysis

All materials except sugar were washed to remove dust, stones, sand, and any other impurities, and then dried for 4 hours at 50°C before milling into flour. After milling, it was analyzed for physico-chemical properties, proximate analysis, minerals, and vitamins. For physico-chemical analysis, the parameters analyzed were bulk density, angle of repose, water absorption and water solubility indices, and oil absorption index. For proximate analysis, parameters include moisture contents, ash, crude protein, and fats. The minerals analyzed were iron, zinc, copper, magnesium, calcium, manganese, potassium, and sodium. Also, vitamin A and total phenol were analyzed.

Determination of Bulk density

Bulk density was measured according to Hasmadi (2021) with slight modification.

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Angle of Repose was determined by Fixed Funnel Method as explained by Brian (2018). Flour material was poured through a funnel to form a cone. The tip of the funnel should be held close to the growing cone and slowly raised as the pile grows, to minimize the impact of falling particles. Stop pouring the material when the pile reaches a predetermined height or the base a predetermined width. Then Angle of Repose is given by the equation

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Protein sample was determined by Kjeldahl method, as described in AOAC (2000). According to this method, samples were digested by heating with concentrated sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄) in the presence of Kjeldahl catalyst. The mixture was then made alkaline and distilled into a boric acid solution. The borate ions formed was titrated against standard sulphuric acid 0.05N, which is converted to total nitrogen in the sample, then multiplied by 6.25 conversion factor to crude protein.

-Determination of fat content (AOAC, 2000)

Total fat was determined by using Soxhlet ether extraction official method 922.06 (AOAC, 2000). Five (5) g of flour sample were placed into the extraction thimble and assembled to the Soxhlet apparatus. The petroleum ether 70 mL were used for continuous reflux for 55 min in three phases, the boiling phase for 15 min, the rinsing phase for 30 min and petroleum ether recovery phase for 10 min. The remaining Petroleum ether was then evaporated. Pre-weighed cups containing fat were dried in an oven at 105°C for 1 hr to evaporate any remaining petroleum ether, cooled in a desiccator for 30 min and weighed. Percentage fat was calculated by using the formula:

$$\% \text{ Fat Content} = \frac{\text{Weight of crude fat(g)}}{\text{Weight of samples(g)}}$$

Micronutrients analysis

-Vitamin A (β -Carotene)

Beta carotene determination was done according to Delia and Mieko (2004), with slightly modifications, where 2.0 g homogenized sample taken into Polytron bottle was extracted by using 50mLs of cold acetone. Then the portions of extracts were transferred into the separating funnel contained 25 mL of petroleum ether (40-60°C Bp) for partitioning, followed by washing with about 125 mL of distilled water until the extracts were acetone free. The washed samples were then passed through anhydrous sodium sulphate to make it free from any trace of water. The dried carotene extracts were then collected into a clean and dry volumetric flask. The extract was then read under UV-Visible Spectrophotometer at 450nm (Double beam UV-3000 model X-ma3000 spectrophotometer Human Corporation, England).

Beta carotene standard solution with the concentration of 110mg/mL was prepared by taking 0.0110g of β -carotene standard powder obtained from Sigma-Adrich into 100mL volumetric flask. 10mL petroleum ether added and swirled to dissolve and finely petroleum ether added until the volume made to 100mL mark of the volumetric flask. Serial dilution of 0mg/mL, 0.1mg/mL, 0.2mg/mL, 0.4mg/mL and 0.6mg/mL were prepared by taking 0mL, 0.2mL, 0.4mL, 0.8mL and 1.0mL of the stock standard solution (110mg/mL) into 25mL volumetric flask. Petroleum ether added to complete volumes (25mL).

Absorbencies of the diluted standards read and standard calibration plot constructed the linear regression equation obtained which will be used to calculate the Beta carotene content of the samples (Rasaki, 2009).

-Minerals

One (1.0) g of homogenized sample weighed into clean pre-treated porcelain crucible. Incinerated into muffle furnace at 450°C for four hours. The obtained ashes of the sample are then dissolved with 10mL of 6% Hydrochloric acid solution, filtered using No. 1 Whatman filter papers and diluted to 100mL with distilled water. The filtrates are then read in Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (UNICAM 919 AAS, England) for Iron and Zinc at 248.3nm and 219.81nm respectively (AOAC 1999 Meth. No. 999.10A).

-Shelf-life study

Shelf-life study was scheduled for five months (December-July 2024). Briefly, the composite flour samples (extruded and non-extruded) of about 250 g were packed in PPNc film bags, paper, and polyethene bags of about 20 cm by 20 cm. The samples were incubated at two different temperatures: room temperature (23±3°C) and refrigerated temperature (4°C) for five months. The relative humidity in both conditions was monitored. The samples were removed after fifteen-day intervals and analysed for changes in quality. The experiment were arranged in three factors in a completely randomised design (CRD) and replicated three times. There are the three factors used in this experiment were storage temperature, packaging materials and storage time. Three levels for packaging materials (PPNc film bags, paper bag, and polyethene bags), two levels of storage temperature (4 and 23°C) and eleven levels of time (0, 15, 30, 45, 60, 75, 90, 105, 120, 135, and 150 days). For samples packaged in PPNc film, the primary packaging was film but the secondary packaging was paper.

4. Control procedures

All analytical determinations were carried out in duplicate to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

5. References

- AOAC. (1999). Official Method 999.10. Lead, Cadmium, Zinc, Copper, and Iron in Foods.
- Delia B. Rodriguez-Amaya and Mieko Kimura (2004). Harvestplus Handbook for carotenoids analysis. International Centre for Tropical Agriculture (CIAT). Washington, DC.
- Hasmadi, M. (2021) Effect of water on the caking properties of different types of wheat flour. Food Technology and Bioprocessing Program, Faculty of Food Science and Nutrition, Universiti Malaysia Sabah, 88400 Kota Kinabalu, Sabah, Malaysia. *Food Research* 5 (1): 266-270.
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2.2. ISACM

2.2.1. Composite flours with novel local varieties: wheat; legumes (pea, faba bean, chickpea) (prototype n. 11a)

2.2.2. Composite flours with novel local varieties: vegetables composite flours (leaf: parsley, spinach, chard; bulb: potato, carrot; spice: tomato, onion) (prototype n. 11b)

DETERMINATION OF DRY MATTER IN RAW MATERIALS / COMPOSITE FLOURS

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Ismahen Essaidi, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, saidi.ismahen@gmail.com;

Maissa Hamrouni, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, maissahm099@gmail.com.

2. Purpose

Evaluate the dry matter of raw materials: the used flours are wheat, pea, faba bean, chickpea; parsley, spinach, chard, potato, carrot, tomato and onion.

3. Principle

Based on oven Drying.

4. Definitions and abbreviations

DM: dry matter

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

N/A: Not Available

5.2. Equipment, instruments

- Oven TCN 50 with digital indicator manufactured by AgroLAB.
- Electronic balance OHAUS with digital indicator

5.3. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

N/A

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

- Five g of each sample are placed in weighed capsules.

6.2. Analysis

- Samples were placed in an oven at 105°C for 24 hours.

6.3. Schematic of method

N/A

6.4. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

N/A

7. Control procedures

All analytical determinations were carried out in triplicate to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

8. Calculations and data analysis

The calculation of the dry matter is carried out according to the following equation:

$$DM (\%) = [(M2-M1)/M0] \times 100$$

M0: mass of the tested sample

M1: empty capsules mass

M2: mass of the capsule with the dried flour

9. References

-Official Methods of Analysis (1995) 16th edn, sec. 33.2.11, Method 991.20. AOAC international, Gaithersburg, MD

DETERMINATION OF ASH CONTENT IN RAW MATERIALS

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Ismahen Essaidi, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, saidi.ismahen@gmail.com

Maissa Hamrouni, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, maissahm099@gmail.com.

2. Purpose

Evaluate the ash content of the different vegetable's flours.

3. Principle

Combustion of the organic matter.

4. Definitions and abbreviations

N/A

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

N/A

5.2. Equipment, instruments

- Muffle furnace
- Electronic balance OHAUS with digital indicator

5.3. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

The use of gloves and crucible tongs as a protective equipment is obligatory.

6. Procedures

6.1 Sample preparation

One g of the different flours is weighed in tarred crucibles.

6.2 Analysis

The samples are incinerated in a muffle furnace at 550°C. for 6 hours until complete combustion of the organic matter, then, the obtained residue is weighed.

6.3 Schematic of method

N/A

6.4 Instrumentation: analytical conditions

7. Control procedures

All analytical determinations were carried out in triplicate to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

8. Calculations and data analysis

The ash content is expressed in % as means \pm standard deviation.

9. References

-Association of Official Analytical Chemist. Official Methods of Analysis. 18th ed. Washington DC; 2005.

DETERMINATION OF PROTEINS IN RAW MATERIALS

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Ismahen Essaidi, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, saidi.ismahen@gmail.com; Dr. Souhir Ben Abdsslem, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, souhirabdsslem2006@gmail.com.

2. Purpose

Quantification of proteins content of wheat and legumes flours.

3. Principle

The principle is based on staining the proteins in the solution with Coomassie blue G250. Once bound to proteins, its colour changes from red to blue. The colour intensity is proportional to the amount of protein present in the sample.

4. Definitions and abbreviations

BSA: bovine albumin serum.

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

- - Coomassie brilliant blue G-250
- -phosphoric acid (85%)
- -BSA

5.2. Equipment, instruments

- Spectrophotometer DRAWELL
- pH-meter
- Electronic balance OHAUS with digital indicator

5.3. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

For the health safety, the use of gloves and mask is obligatory in addition to the manipulation under the hood.

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

Bradford's reagent preparation: the staining reagent is prepared by dissolving 100 mg of Coomassie brilliant blue G-250 in 50 mL of 95% ethanol. A volume of 130 mL of phosphoric acid (85%) is added and the solution is made up to 1 L with distilled water and filtered on filter paper. The pH value of the colouring reagent is adjusted by adding concentrated phosphoric acid until a value of 0.4 is reached. The reagent is then stored at 4°C.

For the sample preparation 1g of flour is macerated with 25mL of physiological water on the ice cube, then filtered using filter paper. 1mL of the filtrate is diluted in 99 mL of distilled water, then a volume of 200 μ l is mixed with 2 mL of Bradford's reagent.

6.2. Analysis

The contents of the tube are mixed thoroughly, and the absorbance is measured after 5 min of standing in the spectrophotometer at 595 nm using distilled water as a blank.

6.3. Schematic of method

N/A

6.4. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

N/A

7. Control procedures

All analytical determinations were carried out in triplicate to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

8. Calculations and data analysis

The protein content is calculated from a standard curve of BSA and the final result is expressed in %.

9. References

-Kruger N.J. The Bradford method for protein quantitation. *Methods Mol. Biol.* 1994; 32:9-15.PubMed

DETERMINATION OF COLOUR PARAMETERS IN RAW MATERIALS / COMPOSITE FLOURS

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Ismahen Essaidi, High Agronomic Institute Of Chott Mariem, saidi.ismahen@gmail.com.

2. Purpose

Determine the colour parameters (L^* , a^* and b^*).

3. Principle

The colour coordinates L^* a^* b^* represent a system of colour quantification where: the value of the L^* parameter represents the variation of the black and white colour, it corresponds to 100 for white and 0 for black.

The value of the a^* parameter varies between (-60) and (+60) indicating, respectively, the dominance of green and red.

The value of the b^* parameter also varies from (-60) for shades of blue, to (+60) for shades of yellow.

4. Definitions and abbreviations

N/A

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

N/A

5.2. Equipment, instruments

- Chromameter Konica Minolta CR-400 Holdings Inc., Japon.

5.3. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

N/A

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

N/A

6.2. Analysis

The colour parameters (L^* , a^* and b^*) of the flours are determined by Minolta CR-400 chromameter.

6.3. Schematic of method

N/A

6.4. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

N/A

7. Control procedures

All analytical determinations were carried out in six replicates to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

8. Calculations and data analysis

N/A

9. References

-Guo X.N., Wu S.H., and Zhu KX. (2020). Effect of superheated steam treatment on quality characteristics of whole wheat flour and storage stability of semi-dried whole noodle. Food chemistry, 322, 126738. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2020.126738>

DETERMINATION OF CHEMICAL COMPOSITION: TOTAL PHENOLS IN RAW MATERIALS / COMPOSITE FLOURS

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Ismahen Essaidi, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, saidi.ismahen@gmail.com; Dr. Souhir Ben Abdsslem High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, souhirabdsslem2006@gmail.com; Maissa Hamrouni, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, maissahm099@gmail.com.

2. Purpose

The purpose of the analysis is to evaluate de bioactive compounds in the different flours.

3. Principle

This assay is based on the spectrophotometric quantification of the total concentration of hydroxyl groups which characterize the polyphenols in the extract.

4. Definitions and abbreviations

TPC: total phenols content

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

- Folin Ciocalteu diluted (1/10)
- Sodium carbonate (7.5%, p /v)
- Gallic acid for the calibration curve

5.2. Equipment, instruments

UV/VIS Spectrophotometer DRAWELL, micropipettes.

5.3. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

N/A

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

5g of flour are macerated in 45mL of distilled water for 30min. The mixture is centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 20 min and then filtered to be used for subsequent analyzes (Mokrani and Madani, 2016).

6.2. Analysis

The amount of TPC in flour's extracts is determined according to the Folin Ciocalteu method as described by Mokrani and Madani, (2016).

Samples (200 μ L) are introduced into test tubes in which 1.0 mL of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (previously diluted x 10 with water) and 0.8 mL of sodium carbonates (7.5%, p/v) are added. The tubes are mixed and left to stand in the dark at room temperature for 30 min. Absorption at 765 nm against a blank is measured using a UV/VIS Spectrophotometer.

6.3. Schematic of method

N/A

6.4. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

N/A

7. Control procedures

All analytical determinations were carried out in triplicate to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

8. Calculations and data analysis

The total phenol content is expressed in mg of gallic acid equivalents per 100 g of dry weight (mg GAE/100 g DM) using a calibration curve. All measurements were performed in triplicate.

9. References

-Mokrani, A., & Madani, K. (2016). Effect of solvent, time and temperature on the extraction of phenolic compounds and antioxidant capacity of peach (*Prunus persica* L.) fruit. Separation and Purification Technology, 162, 68-76. DOI: 10.1016/j.seppur.2016.01.043.

DETERMINATION OF CHEMICAL COMPOSITION: FLAVONOIDS IN RAW MATERIALS

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Ismahen Essaidi, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, saidi.ismahen@gmail.com;
Maissa Hamrouni, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, maissahm099@gmail.com.

2. Purpose

Evaluate the total flavonoids content.

3. Principle

The total flavonoid content was estimated according to the procedure described by Mokrani and Madani based on the formation of aluminium chloride complex.

4. Definitions and abbreviations

TFC: total flavonoids content

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

- Methanolic solution of $AlCl_3$
- Quercitin for the calibration curve

5.2. Equipment, instruments

- UV/VIS Spectrophotometer DRAWELL, micropipettes.

5.3. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

Five g of flour are macerated in 45mL of distilled water for 30min. The mixture is centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 20 min and then filtered to be used for subsequent analyzes (Mokrani and Madani, 2016).

6.2. Analysis

For 1 mL of flour extract, 1 mL of 2% (w/v) methanolic solution of $AlCl_3$ is added. The mixture is left to react for 10 minutes at room temperature and the absorbance was read at 410 nm against a blank.

6.3. Schematic of method

N/A

6.4. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

N/A

7. Control procedures

All analytical determinations were carried out in triplicate to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

8. Calculations and data analysis

The total flavonoid content is calculated from a calibration curve and the results are expressed in equivalent mg of quercetin per 100 g of dry weight (mg QE/100 g DM). All measurements are performed in triplicate.

9. References

-Mokrani, A., & Madani, K. (2016). Effect of solvent, time and temperature on the extraction of phenolic compounds and antioxidant capacity of peach (*Prunus persica* L.) fruit. Separation and Purification Technology, 162, 68–76. DOI:10.1016/j.seppur.2016.01.043

DETERMINATION OF ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY: DPPH SCAVENGING IN RAW MATERIALS/COMPOSITE FLOURS

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Ismahen Essaidi, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, saidi.ismahen@gmail.com; Dr. Souhir Ben Abdsslem High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, souhirabdsslem2006@gmail.com; Maissa Hamrouni, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, maissahm099@gmail.com.

2. Purpose

Evaluate the radical scavenging capacity of the tested flours.

3. Principle

The method adopted for the DPPH test is that of Lee et al., 2004 with some modifications.

4. Definitions and abbreviations

DPPH: 2,2-diphenyl 1-picrylhydrazyl.

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

DPPH methanolic solution

5.2. Equipment, instruments

- UV/VIS Spectrophotometer DRAWELL, micropipettes.

5.3. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

The extract preparation is the same as described for total phenol content.

6.2. Analysis

One mL of the methanolic solution of DPPH (0.1 mM) is added to a volume of 1 mL of each aqueous solution of the extracts at different concentrations. The tubes are left in the dark and at room temperature for 30 minutes. The absorbance reading is taken against a blank at $\lambda=517$ nm.

6.3. Schematic of method

6.4. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

7. Control procedures

All analytical determinations were carried out in triplicate to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

8. Calculations and data analysis

The inhibition percentage of DPPH is given by the following formula:

$$IP(\%) = [1 - (\text{Abs}_{\text{sample}} / \text{Abs}_{\text{control}})] * 100$$

IP%: Inhibition percent of DPPH radicals

Abs_{Control}: absorbance of the control containing 1mL of distilled water and 1mL of the DPPH solution

Abs_{Sample}: Absorbance of the sample

The values of the inhibitor concentration IC₅₀, concentration of antioxidant necessary to reduce 50% of the DPPH radicals, were determined graphically by logarithmic regression.

9. References

-Lee JY., Hwang WI., Lim ST. (2004). Antioxidant and anticancer activities of organic extracts from *Platycodon grandiflorum* A. de Candolle roots. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 93 (2-3), 409-415. DOI: 10.16/j.jep.2004. 04.017.

DETERMINATION OF ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY: FRAP IN RAW MATERIALS

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Ismahen Essaidi, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, saidi.ismahen@gmail.com; Dr. Souhir Ben Abdsslem High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, souhirabdsslem2006@gmail.com; Maissa Hamrouni, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, maissahm099@gmail.com.

2. Purpose

Determine the capacity of flour extract to reduce iron.

3. Principle

The ferric reducing power of flour extracts is determined using the potassium ferricyanide-ferric chloride method (Mokrani and Madani, 2016).

4. Definitions and abbreviations

FRAP: ferric reducing activity power

TCA: trichloroacetic acid

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

- Phosphate buffer (0.2 M, pH 6.6)
- Trichloroacetic acid (10%)
- FeCl₃ (0.1%)
- Potassium ferricyanide (1%)

5.2. Equipment, instruments

- UV/VIS Spectrophotometer
- DRAWELL, micropipettes.

5.3. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

N/A

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

The extract preparation is the same as described for total phenol content.

6.2. Analysis

1 mL of extract is mixed with 2.5 mL of phosphate buffer (0.2 M, pH 6.6) and 2.5 mL of potassium ferricyanide at 1% (w/v).

The mixtures are incubated at 50°C for 20 minutes, after which 2.5 mL of 10% (w/v) TCA are added. 2.5 mL of the mixture is removed and mixed with 2.5 mL of distilled water and 0.5 mL of 0.1% (w/v) FeCl₃. Blue-green colour intensity is measured at 700 nm against a blank.

6.3. Schematic of method

N/A

6.4. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

N/A

7. Control procedures

All analytical determinations were carried out in triplicate to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

8. Calculations and data analysis

The iron-reducing activity is expressed in mg/m

Values are presented as the average of three replicates.

The inhibitor concentration IC_{50} represents the effective concentration to reduce 50% of iron is determined using linear regression.

9. References

-Mokrani, A., & Madani, K. (2016). Effect of solvent, time and temperature on the extraction of phenolic compounds and antioxidant capacity of peach (*Prunus persica* L.) fruit. *Separation and Purification Technology*, 162, 68–76. DOI:10.1016/j.seppur.2016.01.043

DETERMINATION OF TECHNO-FUNCTIONAL PROPERTIES: FLUIDITY IN RAW MATERIALS/COMPOSITE FLOURS BULK DENSITY AND TAPPED DENSITY

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Ismahen Essaidi, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, saidi.ismahen@gmail.com;

Maissa Hamrouni, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, maissahm099@gmail.com

2. Purpose

Every flour has specific characteristics and react differently depending on various factors for that the purpose of this analysis is to characterize the specific parameters of the different flours.

3. Principle

Tapped density is determined according to Bala et al. (2020).

The Carr compressibility index (CI) and the Hausner ratio (HR) are calculated according to the method of Carr (1965) and Hausner (1967)

4. Definitions and abbreviations

The compressibility index (CI)

Bulk density (ρ_b)

Tapped density (ρ_t)

Hausner ratio (HR)

M: flour weight

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

N/A

5.2. Equipment, instruments

- Electronic balance with digital indicator
- Graduated test tube

5.3. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

N/A

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

N/A

6.2. Analysis

The bulk density (ρ_a) of the samples was determined by filling a flour sample into a container of known volume (V_0) (10 mL graduated test tube pre-weighed with a minimum count of 0.5 mL). The weight and volume of the contents is noted.

The volume sampled (V_f) is calculated from the equation after pressing the measuring test tube having a known amount of sample, twenty times on a flat surface of the tabletop.

6.3. Schematic of method

6.4. Instrumentation

N/A

6.5. Analytical conditions

N/A

7. Control procedures

All analytical determinations were carried out in triplicate to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

8. Calculations and data analysis

Bulk density (ρ_a) (kg/m^3) = M/V_0

Tapped density (ρ_t) (kg/m^3) = M/V_f

CI = $[\rho_t - \rho_a] / \rho_t \times 100$

RH = ρ_t / ρ_a

9. References

- Bala M., Handa S., Mridula D, Singh R.K. (2020). Physicochemical, functional and rheological properties of grass pea (*Lathyrus sativus* L.) flour as influenced by particle size. Heliyon 6, e05471 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020>.

DETERMINATION OF FUNCTIONAL PROPERTIES: FLUIDITY IN RAW MATERIALS / COMPOSITE FLOURS, WATER ABSORPTION CAPACITY (WAC), WATER SOLUBILITY INDEX (WSI) AND OIL ABSORPTION CAPACITY (OAC)

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Ismahen Essaidi, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, saidi.ismahen@gmail.com; Dr. Souhir Ben Abdsslem High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, souhirabdsslem2006@gmail.com; Maissa Hamrouni, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, maissahm099@gmail.com

2. Purpose

Evaluate the water capacity, the water solubility and oil absorption capacity as indicators of the flour quality

3. Principle

The water absorption capacity (WAC) and the water solubility index (WSI) are determined by the method of Kadan et al. (2008). For the estimation of oil absorption capacity (OAC) the method of Olu et al., 2012 is used.

4. Definitions and abbreviations

WAC: water absorption capacity

WSI: water solubility index

OAC: oil absorption capacity

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.2. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

N/A

5.3. Equipment, instruments

- Electronic balance with digital indicator
- Centrifuge tubes 50mL
- Centrifuge apparatus Centribot A16.
- Oven TCN 50 with digital indicator manufactured by AgroLAB.

5.4. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

6.2. Analysis

For water absorption capacity (WAC) and the water solubility index (WSI) 2 g of flour are taken into a pre-weighed centrifuge tube and to it 20 mL of distilled water are added. The suspension is kept for 2 h at ambient temperature with occasional shaking then centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 10 min. The supernatant was carefully poured into petri dishes and kept for the estimation of the water solubility index (WSI). Wet sediment weight was measured.

The supernatant obtained during the estimation of the WAC is dried at 105°C. overnight and weighed.

For the estimation of oil absorption capacity (OAC), 2.5 g of sample is mixed with 25 mL of peanut oil in a pre-weighed centrifuge tube. The mixture is stirred for 1 min followed by centrifugation at 4000 rpm (20 min). After that, the extra oil is decanted and the contents of the tube are weighed.

6.3. Schematic of method

N/A

6.4. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

N/A

7. Control procedures

All analytical determinations were carried out in triplicate to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

8. Calculations and data analysis

The WAC is calculated as below:

$$\text{WAC (g/g)} = \frac{\text{mass of sediment}}{\text{dry mass of flour}}$$

The water solubility index (WSI) is calculated as follows:

$$\text{WSI (\%)} = \left[\frac{\text{mass of dried supernatant}}{\text{dry mass of flour}} \right] \times 100$$

The OAC is calculated as follows:

$$\text{OAC (g/g)} = \frac{\text{mass of oil absorbed}}{\text{mass of sample}}$$

9. References

- Kadan R.S., Bryant R.J., Miller J.A. Effects of milling on functional properties of rice flour. *J.Food Sci.* 2008;73(4):E151–E154.
- Olu M., Ogunmoyela O.A.B., Adekoyeni O.O., Jimoh O., Oluwajoba S.O., Sobanwa M.O. Rheological and functional properties of soy-poundo yam flour. *Int.* 2012;2(6):101–107

DETERMINATION OF FUNCTIONAL PROPERTIES: SWELLING INDEX AND SWELLING CAPACITY IN RAW MATERIALS / COMPOSITE FLOURS

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Ismahen Essaidi, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, saidi.ismahen@gmail.com; Dr. Souhir Ben Abdsslem High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, souhirabdsslem2006@gmail.com; Maissa Hamrouni, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, maissahm099@gmail.com.

2. Purpose

Evaluate the swelling index and the swelling capacity as indicators of the flour quality

3. Principle

Based on the measurement of flour volume after immersion in water.

4. Definitions and abbreviations

Swelling index (SI)

Swelling capacity (SC)

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

N/A

5.2. Equipment, instruments

- Electronic balance with digital indicator
- Vortex mixer
- Test tube volume 100mL

5.3. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

N/A

6. Procedures

6.1 Sample preparation

N/A

6.2 Analysis

The swelling index (SI) of flour samples is determined by the method described by (Bala et al., 2020). The sample is added up to 10mL in a pre-weighed 100mL graduated cylinder. The cylinder is weighed again to obtain the sample weight. Distilled water is added up to the 50 mL mark and mixed well using a vortex mixer to homogenize the sample. The mixture is left to stand for 3 h.

6.3 Schematic of method

N/A

6.4 Instrumentation: analytical conditions

N/A

7. Control procedures

All analytical determinations were carried out in triplicate to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

8. Calculations and data analysis

The swelling index (SI) was calculated as follows:

$$SI = (\text{Volume of sample after soaking} - \text{Volume of sample before soaking}) / \text{mass of sample.}$$

The wet sediment obtained from the swelling index determination is used in the calculation of the swelling capacity

The swelling capacity (SC) is calculated using the following formula:

$$SC (\%) = (\text{mass of wet sediment} / \text{mass of sample}) \times 100$$

9. References

-Bala M., Handa S., Mridula D, Singh R.K. (2020). Physicochemical, functional and rheological properties of grass pea (*Lathyrus sativus* L.) flour as influenced by particle size. *Heliyon* 6, e05471. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020>.

DETERMINATION OF FUNCTIONAL PROPERTIES: FOAMING CAPACITY AND FOAMING STABILITY IN RAW MATERIALS / COMPOSITE FLOURS

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Ismahen Essaidi, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, saidi.ismahen@gmail.com; Dr. Souhir Ben Abdsslem High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, souhirabdsslem2006@gmail.com; Maissa Hamrouni, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, maissahm099@gmail.com.

2. Purpose

Evaluate the foaming capacity and the foaming stability of the different flours

3. Principle

Based on the measurement of the foam volume

4. Definitions and abbreviations

Foaming capacity (FC)

Foaming stability (FS)

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

N/A

5.2. Equipment, instruments

- Beaker (250mL)

- Graduated test tube (100 mL)

6. Procedures

6.1 Sample preparation

N/A

6.2 Analysis

Foaming capacity (FC) and Foaming stability (FS) were determined by the method of Kaur and Singh, 2005 with some modifications. 1 g of flour is taken from a 250 mL beaker and 50 mL of distilled water is added to it. The contents are stirred for 1 min using a household mixer. Immediately, the contents are transferred to a 100 mL graduated test tube.

7. Control procedures

All analytical determinations were carried out in triplicate to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

8. Calculations and data analysis

The final foam volume (mL) is noted and the flour foaming capacity is calculated as follows:

$$FC = [(Foam\ volume\ after\ whipping - foam\ volume\ before\ whipping) / Foam\ volume\ after\ whipping] \times 100$$

Foam stability (FS) is determined by measuring the decrease in foam volume (mL), every 10 min for 1 h. It is calculated using the formula:

$$FS = \text{foam volume after one hour} / \text{initial foam volume}$$

9. References

-Kaur M. and Singh N. (2005). Studies on functional, thermal and pasting properties of flours from different Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) cultivars. Food Chemistry 91(3):403-411, DOI:[10.1016/j.foodchem.2004.06.015](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2004.06.015)

DETERMINATION OF SENSORY PROPERTIES IN FOOD PRODUCT (SOUP)

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Ismahen Essaidi, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, saidi.ismahen@gmail.com;
Maissa Hamrouni, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, maissahm099@gmail.com

2. Purpose

It aims to evaluate the consumer acceptance.

3. Principle

Based on hedonic evaluation of sensory attributes (colour, taste, after taste, smell, appearance, texture and overall acceptance) with 7 points scale with 1=I hate extremely and 7= I like extremely.

4. Definitions and abbreviations

N/A

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

N/A

5.2. Equipment, instruments

N/A

5.3. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

The panelists are asked for any allergies before starting the test.

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

Different soups were prepared using the flour with the best composition with the ratio 1/20 (w/v) and cooked for 20 min then placed in a plastic cup coded with three arbitrary digits.

6.2. Analysis

Twenty panelists (staff and students) familiarized with sensory evaluation have participated in the analysis. The soups were presented randomly to assessors at 37°C who were asked to drink water between samples to avoid aftertaste. The panelists were asked to rate their liking of the soups and filled out the sensory sheet (figure 2.2.2.1).

6.3. Schematic of method

Figure 2.2.2.1 Tasting session at ISA-CM laboratory

6.4. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

N/A

7. Control procedures

N/A

8. Calculations and data analysis

The results are collected in excel table and ANOVA analysis is conducted to evaluate the significant difference between samples.

9. References

-Islam M. R., Biswas M.M.H., Esham M. K. H., Roy P., Khan M. R., Hasan S.M. K. 2023. Jackfruit (*Artocarpus heterophyllus*) by-products a novel source of pectin: Studies on physicochemical characterization and its application in soup formulation as a thickener. *Food Chemistry Advances*, 2, 100273. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.focha.2023.100273> R

DETERMINATION OF MYCOTOXINS IN CEREAL-BASED PRODUCTS

1. Purpose

Evaluate the content of mycotoxins (aflatoxins and ochratoxin A) in cereal-based products

2. Principle

Modified AOAC 991.31 and AOAC 2000.03 methods for the simultaneous determination of total aflatoxins (AFs), aflatoxin B1, and ochratoxin A (OTA) in cereal-based foods by RP-HPLC coupled with fluorescence detection. The AOAC 991.31 and AOAC 2000.03 methods were modified by changing sample preparation steps in the simultaneous determination of AFs and OTA. The same extraction process was used for both AF and OTA analysis.

The method is described by Gazioglu & Kolak (2015).

3. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

3.1 Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

- *Analytical standards of total AFs (AFB1, AFB2, AFG1, and AFG2), OTA, R-Biopharm (Darmstadt, Germany)*
- *Potassium bromide (≥99 purity, 104907),*
- *HPLC grade acetonitrile (≥99.93%purity),*
- *HPLC grade methanol (≥99.9% purity), nitric acid (65% purity), and glacial acetic acid (100% purity)0.1% (v/v) formic acid*
- *Phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) prepared by dissolving PBS tablets (Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany) in distilled water*

Stock solutions that contained 1000 ng/mL total AFs (AFB1, AFB2, AFG1, and AFG2) and 1000 ng/mL OTA were prepared from the purchased AF and OTA certified standards. The working standard solutions were prepared by diluting these stock solutions with methanol or methanol–water (60 + 40, v/v) to achieve different concentrations of mycotoxin mixtures. The calibration curve ranged from 0.08 to 10.00 ng/mL for total AFs and from 0.125 to 10.00 ng/mL for OTA. All prepared solutions were stored at -4°C and kept at room temperature in the dark for 30 min before their use.

3.2 Equipment, instruments

- *Aflaprep and Ochraprep immunoaffinity Columns - R-Biopharm (Darmstadt, Germany)*
- *Shimadzu LC-20AT liquid chromatographic system (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) equipped with a fluorescence detector (RF-20A), autosampler system (SIL-20A), pump (LC-20AT), and column oven (CTO-10AS) and controlled by Lab Solutions software*
- *RP C18 column Cronusil-S ODS2 (4.6 × 250 mm, 100 Å, and 5 µm particle size; Gloucester, UK)*
- *KOBRA Cell electrochemical postcolumn derivatization system (R-Biopharm)*

3.3 Health and Safety and personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

AFs and OTA are toxic substances; therefore, were always manipulated in solution, avoiding the formation of dust and aerosols. Nitrile gloves were used for all procedures

4. Procedures

4.1 Sample preparation

Fo Blank wheat samples were spiked with a suitable amount of mycotoxins to achieve 6.0 and 8.0 µg/kg total AFs, and 3.0 and 8.0 µg/kg OTA. After 30 min at room temperature, the spiked samples were extracted, cleaned up, and analyzed using the modified AOAC 991.31 and AOAC 2000.03 methods. All samples were ground with a blender. Each ground and spiked sample (25 g) was extracted with 125 mL methanol (75%). After blending vigorously for 30 min, the extract was filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper. For AF analysis, 15 mL filtrate was diluted with 30 mL distilled water and 15 mL of the supernatant was passed through an immunoaffinity column without preconditioning. For OTA analysis, 5 mL of the filtrate was diluted with 40 mL distilled water and 45 mL of the supernatant was passed through an immunoaffinity column without preconditioning. After the sample passed, the column was washed with 10 mL distilled water. Then, the column was air-dried and AFs were eluted with 1 mL methanol and OTA eluted with 1.5 mL of methanol–acetic acid (98 + 2, v/v). Finally, 1 mL and 1.5 mL distilled water were added for AFs and OTA, respectively, into a glass vial, and 100 µL of these eluates was directly injected for HPLC.

4.2 Analysis

Acetonitrile–methanol–water for AFs, and methanol–water–acetic acid for OTA were used as mobile phases to equilibrate RP HPLC columns before analyses. The wavelengths of excitation and emission were 365 and 435 nm for AFs, and 333 and 460 nm for OTA, respectively. The injection volume was 100 µL, and flow rate was 1.00 mL/min. Separation was achieved at 30°C under isocratic elution with the following mobile phases: acetonitrile–methanol–water (8 + 38 + 54, v/v/v) with 0.2 g/L potassium bromide, acidified with nitric acid (300 µL/L, 65%) for AF analysis and methanol–water–acetic acid (68.5 + 29 + 2.5, v/v/v) for OTA analysis.

5. Control procedures

A cereal sample not contaminated with mycotoxins was used as a blank sample for spiking.

Analyses of replicate spiked samples provided applicability and verification of the method.

6. Calculations and data analysis

The calculated and expected concentrations (C) of the spiked sample were compared to determine the recovery values using following equation:

$$\text{Recovery, \%} = [C_{\text{spiked sample}}/C_{\text{expected}}] \times 100$$

Results are expressed in µg kg⁻¹.

7. References

49.2.18 AOAC Official Method 991.31 Aflatoxins in Corn, Raw Peanuts, and Peanut Butter: Immunoaffinity Column (Aflatest) Method, <https://doi.org/10.1093/9780197610145.003.3973>

49.6.04 AOAC Official Method 2000.03 Ochratoxin A in Barley: Immunoaffinity Column HPLC, <https://doi.org/10.1093/9780197610145.003.4008>

Gazioğlu, I., & Kolak, U. (2015). Method validation for the quantitative analysis of aflatoxins (B1, B2, G1, and G2) and ochratoxin A in processed cereal-based foods by HPLC with fluorescence detection. Journal of AOAC International, 98(4), 939-945.

2.2.3. Snacks from novel local varieties / species (cookies): wheat; legumes (pea / faba bean / chickpea) (prototype n. 21a)

DETERMINATION OF DRY MATTER IN FOOD PRODUCT

The used method is the same as described in 2.2.1.

DETERMINATION OF BAKING WEIGHT LOSS IN FOOD PRODUCT

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Ismahen Essaidi, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, saidi.ismahen@gmail.com; Dr. Souhir Ben Abdsslem High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, souhirabdsslem2006@gmail.com.

2. Purpose

It aims to evaluate the weight loss after baking.

3. Principle

Based on measurement of the weight of cookies.

4. Definitions and abbreviations

Weight loss: WL

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

N/A

5.2. Equipment, instruments

- Digital balance

5.3. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

N/A

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

N/A

6.2. Analysis

The weight of 10 cookies is measured

6.3. Schematic of method

N/A

6.4. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

N/A

7. Control procedures

The determination was carried out in 10 replicates to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

8. Calculations and data analysis

The WL is calculated of percentage as follows:

$(\text{mass of cookies after baking} / \text{mass before baking}) * 100$

9. References

N/A

DETERMINATION OF COLOUR IN FOOD PRODUCT

The used method is the same as described in 2.2.1

DETERMINATION OF COOKIES DIMENSIONS

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Ismahen Essaidi, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, saidi.ismahen@gmail.com; Dr. Souhir Ben Abdsslem High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, souhirabdsslem2006@gmail.com

2. Purpose

It aims to evaluate the dilatation of cookies during baking.

3. Principle

Based on measurement of the diameter and the thickness of cookies.

4. Definitions and abbreviations

Diameter: D; thickness (T)

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1 Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

N/A

5.2. Equipment, instruments

- Digital Calliper

5.3. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

N/A

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

N/A

6.2. Analysis

The diameter and the thickness of 10 cookies is measured.

6.3. Schematic of method

N/A

6.4. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

7. Control procedures

The determination was carried out in 10 replicates to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

8. Calculations and data analysis

The calculated parameter is the spread ratio (D/T)

9. References

-Ud Din G.M., Hussain A., Ashraf H., Tusneem Kausar T., Sidrah H F., Akram S., Ramzan M., Iqbal A., Cacciotti I , Korma S. A.2024. Physicochemical, nutritional and organoleptic characteristics of cookies based on water chestnut (*Trapa natans*) and wheat. *Food chemistry*, 4, 100691. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.focha.2024.100691> R.

DETERMINATION OF TEXTURAL PROPERTIES IN FOOD PRODUCT

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Ismahen Essaidi, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, saidi.ismahen@gmail.com; Dr. Souhir Ben Abdsslem, High Agronomic Institute of Chott, Mariem, souhirabdsslem2006@gmail.com

2. Purpose

It aims to evaluate the textural properties of cookies which are crucial for consumer acceptance.

3. Principle

Based on measurement of different textural parameters (hardness, Adhesiveness, resilience, penetration work)

4. Definitions and abbreviations

Hardness: H; Adhesiveness: A; Resilience: R; penetration work: PW

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1 Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

5.2 Equipment, instruments

Perten texture analyzer TV-6700.

5.3 Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

N/A

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

The entire cookie is used for the test.

6.2. Analysis

A penetration test was applied with cylindrical probe (diameter =2mm), with penetration speed of 5mm/min.

6.3. Schematic of method

N/A

6.4. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

A calibration test should be released before starting the sample's analysis.

7. Control procedures

The determination was carried out in 3 replicates to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

8. Calculations and data analysis

The textural parameters hardness, Adhesiveness, resilience and penetration work were automatically registered in the software.

9. References

DETERMINATION OF PHENOL CONTENT IN FOOD PRODUCT

The used procedure is the same as described in 2.2.1

DETERMINATION OF ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY IN FOOD PRODUCT

The used method is the DPPH radical scavenging test as described in 2.2.1

DETERMINATION OF MICROBIOLOGICAL QUALITY IN FOOD PRODUCT

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Ismahen Essaidi, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, saidi.ismahen@gmail.com; Dr. Souhir Ben Abdsslem, High Agronomic Institute of Chott, Mariem, souhirabdesslem2006@gmail.com

2. Purpose

It aims to evaluate the microbiological quality of cookies which are crucial for product safety.

3. Principle

Based on enumeration the total aerobic mesophilic flora, coliforms and yeasts and moulds.

4. Definitions and abbreviations

Total aerobic mesophilic flora: TAMF, total coliforms: TC, Fecal coliforms: FC, Yeasts and moulds: Y/M.

Plate count agar: PCA, Violet red bile glucose agar: VRBG

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1 Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

- Pepton water, PCA culture medium for TAMF, VRBG for TC and FC, and sabouraud medium for Y/M.

5.2 Equipment, instruments

- Autoclave JSAT65, Bunsen burner, incubators, micropipettes.

5.3 Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

Use of gloves and mask, presence of Fire extinguisher.

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

Different dilutions were prepared ranging from 10^{-1} to 10^{-3} . The first dilution is prepared by mixing 10g of powdered cookies in 90mL of sterilized pepton water then 1 mL of this solution is transferred to a tube containing 10 mL of pepton water to prepare the second dilution.

6.2. Analysis

For TAMF the dilutions 10-2 and 10-3 were considered, 1 mL was transferred to a petri dish and then PCA liquid medium is spread and let to solidify, then incubated at 30°C for 48h. The same procedure is used for coliforms using VRBG as culture medium, TC are incubated at the same conditions of TAMF however FC are incubated at 45°C for 24h. For Y/M, sabouraud medium was solidified in petri dish (20mL) then 100µl of the dilution 10-1 are spread, the incubation conditions were 30°C for 3 days.

6.3. Schematic of method

N/A

6.4. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

N/A

7. Control procedures

8. The determination was carried out in 3 replicates to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy. **Calculations and data analysis**

Only the petri dish containing a number of colonies between 30 and 300 is considered for data calculation.

9. References

-ISO (2006). ISO 4832 Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs - Horizontal method for the enumeration of coliforms - Colony-count technique.

-ISO 21527-1/2:2008 - Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the enumeration of yeasts and moulds. In ISO copyright Office (Ed.), International Standardization Organization (1st ed.). Switzerland.

-ISO 4833-1 Microbiology of the food chain - Horizontal method for the enum Colony count at 30 degrees C by the pour plate technique.

DETERMINATION OF SENSORY PROPERTIES IN FOOD PRODUCT

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Ismahen Essaidi, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, saidi.ismahen@gmail.com; Dr. Souhir Ben Abdsslem, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, souhirabdsslem2006@gmail.com

2. Purpose

It aims to evaluate the sensory characteristic and consumer acceptance of the product

3. Principle

Based on descriptive evaluation of sensory attributes (colour, smell, sweetness taste, salty taste, bitter after taste, texture in hand, texture in mouth and overall acceptance) with 10 points scale with 0=indicates the lowest level of the tested sensory criteria and 10 = the highest level for the tested criteria (figure 2.2)

4. Definitions and abbreviations

N/A

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1 Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

N/A

5.2 Equipment, instruments

N/A

5.3 Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

The panelists are asked for any allergies before starting the test.

6. Procedures

6.1 Sample preparation

At lab scale assay ten samples of cookies with different codes were presented to the panellists (figure 2.2). For industrial scale assay three samples of cookies were presented for sensory evaluation.

6.2 Analysis

30 panelists (staff and students) familiarized with sensory evaluation have participated in the analysis of cookies at lab scale and 60 panelists (staff, students, children from different ages) have tasted the cookies at industrial scale. The coded cookies have been presented to every panelist who filled out the sensory sheet according to his perception level.

6.3 Schematic of method

Figure 2.2.3.1 Cookies preparation for tasting session

6.4 Instrumentation: analytical conditions

N/A

7 Control procedures

N/A

8 Calculations and data analysis

The results are collected in excel table and ANOVA analysis is conducted to evaluate the significant difference between samples

9 References

N/A

DETERMINATION OF ACRYLAMIDE IN FOOD PRODUCTS

1. Purpose

Evaluate the content of acrylamide in cereal based products

2. Principle

Acrylamide is extracted and purified by SPE and then analysed by LC-ESI-MS/MS in positive ion mode (ESI⁺).

3. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

3.1 Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

- *Internal standard solution (¹³C₃-labelled acrylamide in MeOH)*
- *0.1% (v/v) formic acid*
- *Methanol (99.5/0.5, v/v)*
- *Stock solution of acrylamide with water in the 1.5–200 µg/L range*

3.2 Equipment, instruments

- *Agilent 6420 triple quadrupole (Agilent, Santa Clara, United States)*
- *Agilent 1290 Infinity LC Pump equipped with an autosampler and a thermostated column oven*

3.3 Health and Safety and personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

Acrylamide is a known carcinogen and genotoxicant, meaning it can damage DNA and potentially lead to cancer. Proper measures need to be undertaken when managing the analytical standard.

4. Procedures

4.1 Sample preparation

Food samples were finely ground before the extraction.

4.2 Analysis

1 g of sample was weighted into a polypropylene conical tube, and 100 μ L 10 μ g/mL internal standard solution (13 C₃-labelled acrylamide in MeOH) followed by 10 mL 0.1% (v/v) formic acid were added. After mixing with Vortex for 10 min, the extract was centrifuged at 4500 rpm for 15 min. A 2 mL portion of clarified solution was removed, avoiding collection of top oil layer when present, and filtered through paper filter. A solid-phase extraction (SPE) was performed using C18 cartridges (1000 mg, 6 mL; Phenomenex). Cartridges were first conditioned with 5 mL methanol followed by 5 mL water; 1 mL of filtered sample was loaded and washed with 1 mL water. Elution was performed with 1 mL acetone. Acetone was removed under nitrogen flow and sample was dissolved in 1 mL 0.1% (v/v) formic acid before injection. SPE clean-up was performed on 3 extracts for each sample.

HPLC-ESI-MS/MS analysis. LC-ESI-MS/MS in positive ion mode (ESI+) analyses were performed by an Agilent 6420 triple quadrupole (Agilent, Santa Clara, United States) coupled to an Agilent 1290 Infinity LC Pump equipped with an autosampler and a thermostated column oven, according to Calbiani, Careri, Elviri, Mangia, and Zagnoni (2004) with some modifications. The analytical column was a Poroshell 120 C18, 3.0 \times 100 mm, 2.7 μ m (Agilent, USA) maintained at 20 °C. The elution was in isocratic mode using a mixture of 0.1% (v/v) aqueous formic acid and methanol (99.5/0.5, v/v) as mobile phase at a flow rate of 0.3 mL/min. The sample injection volume was 10 μ L. Full-scan analyses were performed in the 40–100 Da mass range, acquiring the following transitions: extracted ion at m/z 55, due to the transition 72 > 55, and at m/z 58, due to the transition 75 > 58 were used for the quantitative analysis. A calibration curve was made for the quantification diluting stock solution of acrylamide with water in the 1.5–200 μ g/L range. For acquisition and processing data, the Agilent MassHunter Workstation software was used.

5. Control procedures

All analytical determinations need to be carried out in triplicate to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

6. Calculations and data analysis

A calibration curve was made for the quantification diluting stock solution of acrylamide with water in the 1.5–200 µg/L range. For acquisition and processing data, the Agilent MassHunter Workstation software was used.

Results are expressed in mg kg⁻¹ of dry weight.

7. References

Calbiani, F., Careri, M., Elviri, L., Mangia, A., & Zagnoni, I. (2004). Development and single-laboratory validation of a reversed-phase liquid chromatography-electrospray tandem mass spectrometry method for identification and determination of acrylamide in foods. Journal of AOAC International, 87(1), 107–115.

2.2.4. Snacks from novel local varieties / species (energetic bars): wheat flasks; dried fruits (apricot, peach, melon) (prototype n. 21b)

A. RAW MATERIALS (FRUITS)

DETERMINATION OF DRY MATTER OF RAW MATERIALS (FRUITS)

The used method is the same as described in 2.2.1. It was evaluated for fresh and dried fruits.

The determination was carried out in 3 replicates to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

DETERMINATION OF TOTAL SOLUBLE SOLIDS (TSS BRUX)

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Ismahen Essaidi, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, saidi.ismahen@gmail.com; Amira Dhief, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, amiradhief707@gmail.com; Baha Khalifa, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, bahakhalifa2000@gmail.com

2. Purpose

It aims to evaluate the soluble solute content

3. Principle

Based on measurement of the Brix

4. Definitions and abbreviations

N/A

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

N/A

5.2. Equipment, instruments

- Juice extractor, Digital refractometer (IP65, PAL-1, ATAGO)

5.3. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

Three batches of fruits are used for juice extraction.

6.2. Analysis

A drop of juice is put on the lenses of the refractometer.

6.3. Schematic of method

N/A

6.4. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

The apparatus must be calibrated using distilled water before starting the sample's analysis

7. Control procedures

For each batch 5 replicates were analysed to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

8. Calculations and data analysis

The results are directly read in the apparatus and expressed as \pm Standard Deviation

9. References

-Rebeaud G., Cioli L., P.Y Cotter, P.Y, Christen D.2023. Cultivar, maturity at harvest and postharvest treatments influence softening of apricots S´everine. *Postharvest Biology and Technology* 195, 112134. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.postharvbio.2022.112134>.

DETERMINATION OF ACIDITY IN RAW MATERIALS (FRUITS)

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Ismahen Essaidi, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, saidi.ismahen@gmail.com; Amira Dhief, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, amiradhief707@gmail.com; Baha Khalifa, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, bahakhalifa2000@gmail.com

2. Purpose

It aims to evaluate the organic acid content.

3. Principle

Based on acid base titration.

4. Definitions and abbreviations

Acidity: A; mass: M

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1 Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

Sodium hydroxide (N/10), phenolphthalein

5.2 Equipment, instruments

- Juice extractor, graduated burette, graduated cylinder

5.3 Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

6. Procedures

6.1 Sample preparation

Three batches of fruit are used for juice extraction

6.2 Analysis

2 mL of juice are titrated with an N/10 sodium hydroxide solution in the presence of a few drops of phenolphthalein. The titration is stopped with the appearance of a pink colour.

6.3 Schematic of method

N/A

6.4 Instrumentation: analytical conditions

N/A

7. Control procedures

For each batch 5 replicates were analysed to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

8. Calculations and data analysis

The results are expressed as follow:

$$\text{Acidity (\%)} = [(100 \times V_s \times c)]/V_0$$

V_0 = volume in mL of the test sample

V_s = volume in mL of the sodium hydroxide solution used for the assay (value read)

c = exact concentration, in moles per litre, of the sodium hydroxide solution (0.1 N)

$$\text{Malic acidity (mgeq/100 g)} = \text{Total acidity} \times 0.67$$

9. References

-Rebeaud G., Cioli L., P.Y Cotter, P.Y, Christen D.2023. Cultivar, maturity at harvest and postharvest treatments influence softening of apricots S´everine. *Postharvest Biology and Technology* 195, 112134. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.postharvbio.2022.112134>

DETERMINATION OF PH IN RAW MATERIALS (FRUITS)

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Ismahen Essaidi, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, saidi.ismahen@gmail.com; Amira Dhief, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, amiradhief707@gmail.com; Baha Khalifa, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, bahakhalifa2000@gmail.com

2. Purpose

It aims to evaluate the pH degree of fruits.

3. Principle

Based on direct measurement of the pH value of fruit juice

4. Definitions and abbreviations

N/A

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1 Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

N/A

5.2 Equipment, instruments

- Juice extractor, pH-meter

5.3 Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

6 Procedures

6.1 Sample preparation

The fruit juice is extracted and directly analysed.

6.2 Analysis

The pH is measured by the probe of the pH meter dipped in 10mL of fruit juice.

6.3 Schematic of method

N/A

6.4 Instrumentation: analytical conditions

The apparatus should be calibrated using standard solutions with pH=4, pH=7

7 Control procedures

Three batches of fruit are used for juice extraction. In every batch five fruits were used.

8 Calculations and data analysis

The results are directly read in the apparatus and expressed as \pm Standard Deviation

9 References

N/A

DETERMINATION OF COLOUR PARAMETERS IN RAW MATERIALS (FRUITS)

The used method is the same as described in 2.2.1. Twenty-five fruits were used for color determination, with two measurements taken for each fruit

DETERMINATION OF FIRMNESS IN RAW MATERIALS (FRUITS)

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Ismahen Essaidi, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, saidi.ismahen@gmail.com; Amira Dhief, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, amiradhief707@gmail.com; Baha Khalifa, High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, bahakhalifa2000@gmail.com

2. Purpose

It aims to evaluate the firmness of the fruits

3. Principle

Based on penetration test

4. Definitions and abbreviations

N/A

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

N/A

5.2. Equipment, instruments

Fruit Texture Analyzer (FTA: Fruit Texture Analyzer - Güss)

5.3. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

20-25 fruits are used for analysis.

6.2. Analysis

The measurement of fruit firmness is conducted with a simple push of a button and the result is read directly in LCD/Keypad attached to the apparatus. Tests are conducted at standard depths and speeds of penetration, ensuring accurate and repeatable analysis.

6.3. Schematic of method

N/A

6.4. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

N/A

7. Control procedures

8. Calculations and data analysis

The results are expressed in kg_{force} and expressed as means \pm Standard Deviation

9. References

N/A

DETERMINATION OF TOTAL PHENOLS IN RAW MATERIALS (FRUITS)

The used method is the same as described in 2.2.1. The analysis was performed in triplicates.

DETERMINATION OF TOTAL FLAVONOIDS IN RAW MATERIALS (FRUITS)

The used method is the same as described in 2.2.1. The analysis was performed in triplicates.

DETERMINATION OF DPPH RADICAL SCAVENGING ACTIVITY IN RAW MATERIALS (FRUITS)

The used method is the same as described in 2.2.1. The analysis was performed in triplicates.

DETERMINATION OF FRAP ACTIVITY IN RAW MATERIALS (FRUITS)

The used method is the same as described in 2.2.1. The analysis was performed in triplicates.

B. ENERGETIC BARS CHARACTERIZATION

DETERMINATION OF DRY MATTER IN FOOD PRODUCT (ENERGETIC BARS)

The used method is the same as described in 2.2.1. The analysis was performed in triplicates.

DETERMINATION OF COLOUR PARAMETERS IN IN FOOD PRODUCT (ENERGETIC BARS)

The used method is the same as described in 2.2.1. The analysis was performed in 10 replicates.

DETERMINATION OF MICROBIOLOGICAL QUALITY IN FOOD PRODUCT (ENERGETIC BARS)

The used method is the same as described in 2.2.2 for cookies microbiological quality. The analysis was performed in triplicates.

DETERMINATION OF TOTAL PHENOLS CONTENT IN FOOD PRODUCT (ENERGETIC BARS)

The used method is the same as described in 2.2.1. The analysis was performed in triplicates.

DETERMINATION OF DPPH RADICAL SCAVENGING ACTIVITY IN FOOD PRODUCT (ENERGETIC BARS)

The used method is the same as described in 2.2.1. The analysis was performed in triplicates.

DETERMINATION OF TEXTURAL PARAMETERS IN FOOD PRODUCT (ENERGETIC BARS)

The used method is the same as described in 2.2.2. The analysis was performed in 10 replicates.

DETERMINATION OF SENSORY CHARACTERISTICS IN FOOD PRODUCT (ENERGETIC BARS)

The used method is the same as described in 2.2.2. The analysis was performed in 10 replicates.

2.3. INAT

2.3.1. Composite flours with novel local varieties: composite flour (prototype n. 11b)

DETERMINATION OF DRIED PRODUCT REHYDRATION CAPACITY

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Sarra Jribi, INAT (TN) sarra.jribi@gmail.com; Raouia Ghanem, INAT (TN) raouia-ghanem@hotmail.fr; Faten Khamassi, INAT (TN) Faten.khamassi@gmail.com; Jamila Ben Souissi, INAT (TN) jbensouissi@yahoo.fr.

2. Purpose

Determine the rehydration capacity different dried samples.

3. Principle

The rehydration capacity of a dried material is determined by measuring the weight of the material before and after rehydration with a liquid (usually water) and calculating the ratio between the weight of the rehydrated sample and the weight of the dried sample.

The principle of rehydration capacity determination involves the following steps:

- Weighing the dried sample: The initial weight of the dried material is measured accurately.
- Rehydration process: The dried sample is immersed in a liquid (e.g., water) for a specific period of time to allow it to reabsorb moisture.
- Weighing the rehydrated sample: After the rehydration process is complete, the sample is removed from the liquid, excess surface moisture is removed, and the final weight of the rehydrated sample is measured.
- Calculation: The rehydration capacity is calculated by dividing the weight of the rehydrated sample by the weight of the dried sample and expressing it as a ratio or percentage.

The rehydration capacity determination provides valuable information about the ability of the dried material to regain moisture and restore some of its original properties after the drying process.

4. Definitions and abbreviations

RC: Rehydration Capacity g: gram; mL: milliliter

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Equipment, instruments and reagents

- Water bath
- Volumetric flasks

- Analytical balance

5.2. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

- Gloves

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

Homogeneous dried samples are selected.

6.2. Analysis

5g of dried product (fruit/vegetable) were added to 200mL distilled water in flask beaker

Rehydration experiments were carried out in a water bath at 30 and 60°C

After the water was drained, the mass of the samples was recorded at every 60 min till the constant mass was obtained.

6.3. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

The analytical balance is calibrated by a professional instrumentalist.

7. Control procedures

- Determination is carried out in triplicates to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

8. Calculations and data analysis

Rehydration capacity (RC) of each sample was calculated as follows:

$$\frac{\text{Weight of rehydrated sample (g)}}{\text{Weight of dried sample (g)}}$$

9. References

-Aral, S., & Beşe, A. V. (2016). Convective drying of hawthorn fruit (*Crataegus* spp.): Effect of experimental parameters on drying kinetics, colour, shrinkage, and rehydration capacity. *Food chemistry*, 210, 577-584.

-Özkan-Karabacak, A., Acoğlu, B., Yolci Ömeroğlu, P., & Çopur, Ö. U. (2020). Microwave pre-treatment for vacuum drying of orange slices: Drying characteristics, rehydration capacity and quality properties. *Journal of Food Process Engineering*, 43(11), e13511.

DETERMINATION OF ASCORBIC ACID CONTENT (VITAMIN C) IN FRUITS AND VEGETABLES USING IODOMETRIC TITRATION

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Wafa Rjiba, INAT (TN) wafa.rjiba@yahoo.fr; Raouia Ghanem, INAT (TN) raouia-ghanem@hotmail.fr; Faten Khamassi, INAT (TN) Faten.khamassi@gmail.com; Jamila Ben Souissi, INAT (TN) jbensouissi@yahoo.fr.

2. Purpose

Determine the content of ascorbic acid in different samples.

3. Principle

The principle behind the determination of vitamin C (ascorbic acid) content in fruits and vegetables using iodometric titration involves the oxidation-reduction reaction between ascorbic acid and iodine. In this method, iodine is used as the titrant, and it reacts with ascorbic acid in the presence of an indicator (such as starch) to form iodide ions and dehydroascorbic acid. The end-point of the titration is reached when all the ascorbic acid has reacted with iodine, and the appearance of a blue-black colour indicates the completion of the reaction.

The amount of iodine consumed in the reaction is stoichiometrically related to the amount of ascorbic acid present in the sample. By titrating a known volume of the sample containing ascorbic acid with iodine solution and determining the volume of iodine required to reach the end-point, the concentration of ascorbic acid in the sample can be calculated.

Overall, iodometric titration is a reliable and cost-effective method for determining the vitamin C content in fruits and other samples due to its simplicity and accuracy

4. Definitions and abbreviations

mg: milligram; mL: milliliter

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

6.1. Equipment, instruments and reagents

- Beakers
- Volumetric flasks
- Analytical balance
- Erlenmeyer flask
- Ascorbic acid
- Starch
- Potassium iodide (KI)
- Potassium iodate (KIO₃)
- Sulfuric acid (3molar)

6.2. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

- Lab coat and gloves

7. Procedures

7.1. Sample preparation

Samples were ground.

Samples for analysis should be homogeneous.

7.2. Analysis

The steps involved in the determination of vitamin C (ascorbic acid) content in fruits using iodometric titration typically include:

- Preparation of Standard Solution: Prepare a standard solution of ascorbic acid with a known concentration (0.25 g ascorbic acid in 250mL of distilled water).
- Preparation of Iodine solution: Iodine Solution was prepared by mixing 5.00 g potassium iodide (KI) and 0.268 g potassium iodate (KIO₃) were dissolved into 500 mL beaker with 200 mL of distilled water. 30 mL of 3molar sulfuric acid was added into the beaker and then diluted with distilled water until 500 mL solution.
- Standardization of Iodine Solution: Standardization of iodine solution with the vitamin C standard solution was by pipetting 25mL of vitamin C solution into a 125 mL Erlenmeyer flask. 10 drops of 1% starch solution were added and then titrated against iodine solution until blue-black colour was observed.
- Titration Process: a. Pipette a known volume of the fruit sample (vegetable) solution into a flask. b. Add a few drops of starch indicator solution to the flask. c. Titrate the sample solution with the standardized iodine solution until a persistent blue-black colour appears.
- Calculation: Calculate the concentration of ascorbic acid in the fruit sample based on the volume of iodine solution used in the titration and the known concentration of the iodine solution.
- Repeat: Repeat the titration process for each fruit sample to ensure accuracy and reproducibility of results.

7.3. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

The analytical balance is calibrated by a professional instrumentalist.

8. Control procedures

- Analysis are carried out in triplicates to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

9. Calculations and data analysis

The vitamin C content is expressed as follows:

$$\frac{\text{Concentration standard (mg/ml)} * 1000}{\text{Weight of sample (g)}}$$

10. References

- Nweze, C. C., M. G. Abdulganiyu, and O. G. Erhabor. "Comparative analysis of vitamin C in fresh fruits juice of *Malus domestica*, *Citrus sinensi*, *Ananas comosus* and *Citrullus lanatus* by iodometric titration. *Int. J. Sci. Environ. Technol.*, 4.1 (2015): 17-22.

2.3.2. Dried products: dried fish (prototype n. 15b), dried vegetables (prototype n. 15c)

DETERMINATION OF TOTAL ASH CONTENT IN FRESH FISH SPECIES

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Wafa Rjiba, INAT (TN) wafa.rjiba@yahoo.fr; Raouia Ghanem, INAT (TN); raouia-ghanem@hotmail.fr; Faten Khamassi, INAT (TN) Faten.khamassi@gmail.com; Jamila Ben Souissi, INAT (TN) jbensouissi@yahoo.fr

2. Purpose

Determine the content of total ash or the total amount of minerals present within a sample.

3. Principle

The total ash content is determined after an incineration at 550°C.

4. Definitions and abbreviations

- Ash is the inorganic residue remaining after the water and organic matter have been removed by heating in the presence, which provides a measure of the total amount of minerals within a sample

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Equipment, instruments

- Grinder
- Desiccator with an efficient dehydrator
- Analytical balance
- Oven set at 105±2°C
- Porcelain incineration crucibles
- Aluminium foil
- Spatula
- Muffle furnace set at 550°C

5.2. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

Lab coat and gloves

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

After weighing, heading, gutting, scaling or skin peeling and filleting fresh fishes, samples were ground. Samples for analysis should be homogeneous.

6.2. Analysis

- Dry the crucibles for 30 min at the oven set at 105±2°C
- After cooling at room temperature in the desiccator, thoroughly weigh the porcelain dish empty with the aluminium lid during incineration. M0 is this weight.
- Homogenize the sample
- Introduce the equivalent of 10 g fresh matter, weighed precisely, in the porcelain crucible and recover it with the aluminium foil. Weigh (M1 is this weight). Put everything in the furnace set at 550°C for at least 5 hours. Ashes must be white or light grey, free of charcoal particles
- Wait for the total cooling of the furnace before opening the door and getting the sampling out.

- Place the crucibles in the desiccator until they reach room temperature. Weigh with accuracy. This weight is noted M2.

6.3. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

The analytical balance is calibrated by a professional instrumentalist.

There are a number of different types of crucibles available for ashing food samples, including quartz, Pyrex, porcelain, steel and platinum. Selection of an appropriate crucible depends on the sample being analysed and the furnace temperature used. The most widely used crucibles are made from porcelain because it is relatively inexpensive to purchase, can be used up to high temperatures (< 1200 °C) and are easy to clean. Porcelain crucibles are resistant to acids but can be corroded by alkaline samples, and therefore different types of crucibles should be used to analyze this type of sample. In addition, porcelain crucibles are prone to cracking if they experience rapid temperature changes.).

It is recommended to use deionized water when preparing samples.

7. Control procedures

- This analysis must be done in triplicates to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.
- Warning: the permanent pen-marker is charred in such temperature conditions. The sample must be identified using another technique and well-spotted in the muffle furnace.

8. Calculations and data analysis

The ash content is expressed as follows:

$$\frac{(M2 - M0) * 100}{M1 - M0}$$

M0: Weigh (g) of the dish + aluminium; M1: Weigh (g) of the crucible + aluminium + sample; M2: Weigh (g) of the crucible + aluminium + sample after incineration

- Take the arithmetic mean of the 3 essays.
- The results must be expressed to the nearest 0.1%

9. References

-Association of Official Analytical Chemists. Official Methods of Analysis of AOAC International; AOAC International: Gaithersburg, MD, USA, 1998.
<https://www.iso.org>

DETERMINATION OF CRUDE PROTEINS IN FISH AND FISH-BASED PRODUCTS

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Wafa Rjiba, INAT (TN) wafa.rjiba@yahoo.fr, Raouia Ghanem, INAT (TN) raouia-ghanem@hotmail.fr, Faten Khamassi, INAT (TN) Faten.khamassi@gmail.com; Jamila Ben Souissi, INAT (TN) jbensouissi@yahoo.fr.

2. Purpose

Determination of overall protein concentration in fish or fish-based product.

3. Principle

The sample is digested with a strong acid so that it releases nitrogen which can be determined by a suitable titration technique. The amount of protein present is then calculated from the nitrogen concentration of the food with a *digestion factor (F)* (6.25, equivalent to 0.16 g nitrogen per gram of protein), however, this is only an average value, and each protein has a different digestion factor depending on its amino-acid composition. The Kjeldahl method can conveniently be divided into three steps: digestion, neutralization and titration.

4. Definitions and abbreviations

F: conversion factor; G: gram; mL: millilitre; DM: dry matter; WM: wet matter

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

- Concentrated sulfuric acid (analytical quality)
- Concentrated sodium hydroxide (NaOH, 10 N)
- Boric acid solution with colour indicator
- Hydrogen Chloride (HCL, 1 N)
- Mineralization catalyst: Wieninger pellets
- MilliQ water

5.2. Equipment, instruments

- Grinder
- Analytical balance
- 10 mL burette graduated 1/20 e mL
- Anti-heat protection gloves
- Kjeldhal Mineralization flasks
- 250 mL Erlenmeyer
- Kjeldahl digester
- Distillation unit
- Titration unit may be combined in Kjeldahl analyser

5.3. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

The wear of a lab coat and gloves is mandatory.

Digestion manipulation must be under lab extractor.

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

After weighing, heading, gutting, scaling or skin peeling and filleting fresh fishes, samples were ground.

Samples for analysis should be homogeneous.

6.2. Analysis

➤ *Digestion*

-The sample to be mineralized (1 g DM or 4 g WM) is weighed with accuracy and placed in Kjeldahl flasks. This weight is designed as M (g).

Add 20 mL sulfuric acid (an oxidizing agent that digests the food) and mineralization pellet (catalyst) in the flask; put the smoke sensors in the flasks, turn water on and heat gradually until 450°C. Digest until clear to get complete breakdown of all organic matter (pale green solution). Leave cooling. Rinse the smoke sensors with MilliQ water that we collect in the flask. Non-volatile ammonium sulphate is formed from the reaction of nitrogen and sulfuric acid:

During digestion, protein nitrogen is liberated to form ammonium ions (NH₄⁺); sulfuric acid oxidizes organic matter and combines with ammonium formed; carbon and hydrogen elements are converted to carbon dioxide and water.

➤ *Neutralization and distillation*

-The digest is diluted with 20 mL MilliQ water.

-Turn on the distillation unit and the water of the cooling system (always check water and NaOH levels)

-Put 20 mL of Boric acid solution in the 250 mL erlenmeyer

-Place the erlenmeyer in the distillation unit and check carefully that the bubble rod

-Place the mineralization flask on the other side of the kjeldahl analyser

-Alkali-containing sodium thiosulfate is added to neutralize the sulfuric acid until obtaining a total volume of 80 mL

-Put the steam on

-Stop when the distilled solution reached 200 mL (6 min per sample)

The solution in the digestion flask is then made alkaline by addition of sodium hydroxide, which converts the ammonium sulphate into ammonia gas:

The ammonia gas that is formed is liberated from the solution and moves out of the digestion flask and into the receiving flask - which contains an excess of boric acid. The low pH of the solution in the receiving flask converts the ammonia gas into the ammonium ion, and simultaneously converts the boric acid to the borate ion:

➤ **Titration**

Titrate the distillate with HCL 1N. The added volume will be noted V (mL). Borate anion (proportional to the amount of nitrogen) is titrated with standardized HCl as follows:

6.3. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

Always be careful of water and NaOH level in the distillation unit before starting the analysis

7. Control procedures

Always check the condition of mineralization flasks. Do not use chipped ones

8. Calculations and data analysis

Total nitrogen content (%N) is given by this formula:

$\frac{(1.4 * V)}{M}$

Protein content for fish samples is given as follows (Crooke et al. 1971):

$6.25 * N$

9. References

- AOAC (1990) Official methods of analysis of the association of chemists. Analysis of the Association of Chemists, Washington, DC, pp 223-225–992-995.
- Crooke; W. M.; Simpson, W. E. Determination of Ammonium in Kjeldahl Digests of Crops by an Automated Procedure. *J. Sci. Food Agric.* 1971, 22 (1), 9–10.
- Saez-Plaza P., Navas M.J., Wybraniec S., Michałowski T., Asuero A.G. (2013) An Overview of the Kjeldahl Method of Nitrogen Determination. Part II. Sample Preparation, Working Scale, Instrumental Finish, and Quality Control. *Critical Reviews in Analytical Chemistry*, 43:224–272.
- ISO. ISO 5983-2: 2009 Animal Feeding Stuffs-Determination of Nitrogen Content and Calculation of Crude Protein Content. Part 2: Block Digestion and Steam Distillation Method.

DETERMINATION OF FAT CONTENT IN FISH AND FISH-BASED PRODUCTS

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Wafa Rjiba, INAT (TN) wafa.rjiba@yahoo.fr; Raouia Ghanem, INAT (TN) raouia-ghanem@hotmail.fr; Faten Khamassi, INAT (TN) Faten.khamassi@gmail.com; Jamila Ben Souissi, INAT (TN) jbensouissi@yahoo.fr

2. Purpose

This method is used for quantitative determination of the fat content of foodstuffs by solvent extraction using a Soxhlet apparatus.

3. Principle

The principle of this method is to extract fat by repeated washing with a solvent, to determine the difference in masses before and after extraction. It consists in the extraction and determination of the content of free fats by hexane, which is eliminated afterwards by evaporation. The residue is dried and weighed after cooling in the desiccators.

4. Definitions and abbreviations

Lipids are usually defined as those components that are soluble in organic solvents (such as ether, hexane or chloroform), but are insoluble in water.

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

- Solvent (Hexane)

5.2. Equipment, instruments

- Soxhlet apparatus (c.f; description in the analysis paragraph)
- Rotavapor
- Analytical balance (0.001g)

5.3. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

- A lab coat and a pair of gloves are mandatory
- Organic solvents tend to be highly flammable. Use appropriate precautions.
- Extraction and post-extraction evaporation steps must be performed in a vented hood!
- Hazardous solvents are used and must be disposed of in appropriate waste containers.

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

The sample preparation for lipid analysis depends on the type of food and the type and nature of lipids in the food. Some preparatory steps are common in lipid analysis:

- *removal of water (pre-drying)
- *reduction of particle size to increase solvent-food contact area

6.2. Analysis

- Measure and record the weight of flask (M1)
- Weigh nearly 10 g of sample on the filter paper and record the value with four digits (M0)
- Insert the sample in extraction thimble to the soxhlet apparatus (extractor), add 250 mL hexane and start the heating. Close the heater at the end of 6 h.
- Evaporate the hexane using rotary vacuum evaporator. There will be only fat at the end of evaporation.
- Measure and record the weight of flask containing oil (M2).

6.3. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

- The analytical balance is calibrated by a professional instrumentalist.

-Ideal solvents for fat extraction should have a high solvent power for lipids and low or no solvent power for proteins, amino acids, and carbohydrates. It should evaporate easily and leave no residue, have a relatively low boiling point and be non-flammable and nontoxic in both liquid and vapor states.

7. Control procedures

- This analysis must be done in triplicates to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.
- Fatty acids are very present on hands. To not measure them, it is therefore essential to wear gloves.

8. Calculations and data analysis

$$\text{Fat \%} = \frac{(M2 - M1) \times 100}{M0}$$

M0: weight of sample; M1: weight of empty flask; M2: weight of flask and lipids

9. References

- AOAC. Official Methods of Analysis (Method 945.16), 15th ed.; Association of Official Analytical Chemists: Washington, DC, 1990.
- Srigley, Cynthia T., Mossoba, Magdi M. (2017) Current Analytical Techniques for Food Lipids. *Food and Drug Administration Papers*, 7.

DETERMINATION OF FATTY ACID PROFILE IN FISH BY GAS CHROMATOGRAPHY

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Wafa Rjiba, INAT (TN) wafa.rjiba@yahoo.fr; Raouia Ghanem, INAT (TN) raouia-ghanem@hotmail.fr; Faten Khamassi, INAT (TN) Faten.khamassi@gmail.com; Jamila Ben Souissi, INAT (TN) jbensouissi@yahoo.fr.

2. Purpose

Gas Chromatography is an analytical procedure used for separating analysing lipid and identifying the chemical structure of the peaks and the fatty acids profile.

3. Principle

A chromatographic analysis involves passing a mixture of the molecules to be separated through a column that contains a matrix capable of selectively retarding the flow of the molecules. Molecules in the mixture are separated because of their differing affinities for the matrix in the column. The stronger the affinity between a specific molecule and the matrix, the more its movement is retarded, and the slower it passes through the column. Thus, different molecules can be separated based on the strength of their interaction with the matrix. After being separated by the column, the concentration of each of the molecules is determined as they pass by a suitable

detector (flame ionization detector). The identification of fatty acid methyl esters was performed by external standards and a complete profile of fatty acids can be determined.

4. Definitions and abbreviations

➤ *Definitions:*

Fatty acids: are comprised of hydrocarbon chain terminating with carboxylic acid groups. Fatty acids and their associated derivatives are the primary components of lipids. The length and degree of saturation of the hydrocarbon chain is highly variable between fatty acid and dictates the associated physical properties (e.g., melting point and fluidity). Moreover, fatty acids are responsible for the hydrophobic properties (insoluble in water) exhibited by lipids.

Fatty acid methyl esters (FAME): are produced by transesterification of fats or oils (triglycerides) with methanol

➤ *Abbreviations:*

GC: Gas Chromatography

FID: Flame Ionisation Detector

FAME: fatty acid methyl esters

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

-Heptane

-Supelco 37 component (FAME Mix)

-Methanol, containing not more than 0,5 % (m/m) of water.

-Potassium hydroxide, methanolic solution, approximately 1 N. Dissolve 5,6 g of potassium hydroxide in 100 L of methanol

-Heptane, of chromatographic quality

-Sodium sulphate, anhydrous.

-Nitrogen, having an oxygen content less than 5 mg/kg

-Sodium methylate, methanolic solution: Dissolve 1 g of sodium in 100 mL of methanol containing not more than 0,5 % of water.

-Hydrochloric acid, anhydrous methanolic solution, approximately 1 N.

-Methyl red, 1 g/l solution in 60 % (V/V) ethanol.

-Nitrogen, having an oxygen content less than 5 mg/kg

5.2. Equipment, instruments

-Gas Chromatograph (Dani Master gas chromatograph) equipped with flame Ionisation Detector (FID)

-Column (Agilent DB-23, 60m x 0,25mm x 0,25um)

-A computer piloting the apparatus and acquiring the signal (GALAXIE)

-High-speed stirrer and appropriate means of heating (for example a magnetic stirrer equipped with a heater).

-Reflux condenser

-Specific glassware (tubes, inserts, corks)

5.3. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

-The methods described involve the use of potentially hazardous reagents. Normal precautions should be taken for eye protection and for protection from the dangers of corrosive chemical burns.

-Because of the toxic character of boron trifluoride, preparation of methanolic solution of boron trifluoride from methanol must be performed under a ventilated hood.

-It is essential to wash all glass ware with water immediately after use.

-Beware the GC detector and injector that may be hot.

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

The sample preparation for lipid analysis depends on the type of food and the type and nature of lipids in the food. Some preparatory steps are common in lipid analysis: the removal of water and the reduction of particle size to increase solvent-food contact area.

6.2. Analysis

Lipid extraction by soxhlet method

Derivatization: Preparation of fatty acid methyl esters (FAMES) using ISO 5509 methylation method

Weigh approximately 4 g of the test sample and introduce the test portion into the flask

✓ Method applicable to neutral fats and oils (acid value less than 2)

-Add about 40 mL of the methanol, 0,5 mL of the methanolic potassium hydroxide solution and a boiling aid then fit the condenser to the flask.

-Bring to the boil. The solution should become clear. The reaction is normally complete after 5 to 10 min.

-Cool the flask under running water, and transfer the contents to a separating funnel

-Rinse the flask into the separating funnel with 20 mL of the heptane

-Add about 40 mL of water, shake and allow to separate. The esters pass into the upper heptane layer. Draw off the aqueous layer into a second separating funnel and extract it again with 20 mL of heptane. Combine the two extracts and wash them twice with 20 mL portions of water. Separate and dry the ester solution over anhydrous sodium sulphate

-Filter through cotton wool into a 50 mL conical flask and evaporate the solution to approximately 20 mL over a boiling water bath, under a stream of nitrogen.

✓ Method applicable to acid fats and oils (acid value greater than 2) and fatty acids

➤ Case of acidic fats and oils

Introduce the test portion into the flask

Add 40 mL of the sodium methylate solution and a boiling aid

Fit the condenser to the flask.

Bring to the boil. The solution should become clear. The reaction is normally complete in less than 15 min.

Add at least 50 mL of the methanolic hydrochloric acid solution to the flask

➤ Case of fatty acids

If the sample consist entirely of fatty acids, the saponification step is not necessary.

Introduce the test portion into the flask

Add 50 mL of the methanolic hydrochloric acid solution and a boiling aid. Fit the condenser to the flask.

Preparation of the methyl esters

-Boil for 10 min, then cool the flask under running water, add 100 mL of water to the flask, then transfer the contents to the 250 mL separating funnel and add 30 mL of the heptane.

-Shake vigorously and allow to settle until the two phases have separated.

-Collect the heptane layer.

-Extract the aqueous phase again with 30 mL of heptane.

-Combine the two heptane extracts and wash them with 20 mL portions of water until free from acid, using the methyl red solution as indicator.

-Dry over anhydrous sodium sulphate.

-Filter through cotton wool into the 100 mL conical flask and evaporate the solution to approximately 20 mL over a boiling water bath, under a stream of nitrogen

CPG analysis:

For the quantitative analysis of each fatty acid, Supelco 37 component (FAME Mix) was used as an external standard. Sample compositions were investigated by Dani Master gas chromatograph and the column (Agilent DB-23, 60m x 0,25mm x 0,25um) equipped with flame Ionization Detector (FID).

The identification of fatty acid methyl esters was performed by external standards and values of fatty acids are presented as g/100 g wet weight

7. Control procedures

For replicates unshouldering all samples in triplicate when sufficient sample is available to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy. Standards and calibration verification standard should be prepared.

All reagents and solvents shall be analytical quality, and the water shall be distilled water or water of equivalent quality.

8. Calculations and data analysis

The detector is connected to a signal acquisition and processing system in which standard fatty acids are calibrated in marine raw materials. Fatty acid contents can be determined in relation to the total amount of fatty acids present.

9. References

-ISO 5509:1978. Animal and vegetable fats and oils - Preparation of methyl esters of fatty acids

DETERMINATION OF MOISTURE CONTENT IN FISH AND FISH-BASED PRODUCTS

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Wafa Rjiba, INAT (TN) wafa.rjiba@yahoo.fr; Raouia Ghanem, INAT (TN) raouia-ghanem@hotmail.fr; Faten Khamassi, INAT (TN) Faten.khamassi@gmail.com; Jamila Ben Souissi, INAT (TN) jbensouissi@yahoo.fr.

2. Purpose

Determine moisture content in fish and fish-based products as percentage of the wet weight.

3. Principle

Water content is determined gravimetrically by removing moisture (oven drying at 105°C until constant weight) and measuring weight loss of the sample (a direct measurement).

4. Definitions and abbreviations

➤ *Definition:*

Moisture content is defined as the mass of water in the sample expressed in % wet basis or % dry basis.

Dry matter refers to material remaining after removal of water.

➤ *Abbreviations*

DM: Dry Matter; g: gram

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Equipment, instruments

- Grinder
- Desiccator with an efficient dehydrator
- Analytical balance (precision 0.1 mg)
- Oven set at 105±2°C
- Metallic cups

5.2. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

- Lab coat and gloves

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

After weighing, heading, gutting, scaling or skin peeling and filleting fresh fishes, samples were ground and then oven dried.

6.2. Analysis

- Dry the metallic cups for 30 min at the oven set at $105\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$
- After cooling at room temperature in the desiccator, weigh accurately the empty metallic cup (M0)
- Homogenize the sample
- Introduce the equivalent of 10 g fresh matter (or adapt according to the quantities available) (M1)
- Put in the oven at $105\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ until constant weight
- Get the capsules out of the oven and place them in the desiccator
- After cooling at room temperature. Weigh the metallic cup with the sample dried inside (M2).

6.3. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

The analytical balance is calibrated by a professional instrumentalist.

7. Control procedures

This analysis must be done in triplicates to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy. The differences of the results made simultaneously by the same analyst must not be superior to 0.1 g of DM per 100 g of sample.

8. Calculations and data analysis

The moisture content is expressed as follows:

$$\frac{M1 - (M2 - M0)}{M1}$$

M0: Weigh (g) of the empty cup; M1: Weigh (g) of the tested sample; M2: Weigh (g) of the cup and the sample after drying

Take the arithmetic mean of the 3 essays

9. References

-AOAC (1980). Official methods of analysis of the association of official analytical chemists. 13th ed., W. Horwitz, ed., 24.003.

2.4. MAK

2.4.1. Composite flours with novel local varieties: orange fleshed sweet potatoes, grain amaranth, amaranth-enriched wheat, and pumpkin (prototype n. 12)

DETERMINATION OF NUTRIENT AND BIOACTIVES CONTENT OF COMPOSITE FLOURS

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

John H. Muyonga, hmuyonga@yahoo.com

2. Purpose

The purpose of the analyses is to determine the macronutrients content as well as the content of iron, zinc and carotenoids of composite flours. This enables the following:

- Determination of the contribution of the flours to human nutrient needs
- Comparison of the nutritional value of the composite flours to other food products
- Evaluate the effect of processing on nutritional value.

3. Principle

The general principles and rationale for the methods used are summarized below.

Analysis	Method and Principle
Moisture content	Direct method using an oven Principle: Loss in mass on drying of a given material under oven conditions gives a measure of moisture present in the material. This is a thermogravimetric method (the weight loss of mass that occurs as the material is heated).
Ash	Combustion of product in muffle furnace at 550°C for 6 hours. Principle: Ashing is done to combust the organic matter and to determine the inorganic matter that remains. Ash yields the original mineral matter (inorganic) in the sample.
Dietary fibre	Digesting sample with acid detergent solution and residue dried in oven using reflux equipment. Principle: The hot acid detergent solution removes the digestible material and soluble fibre thus leaving the least digestible fibre including cellulose and lignin in plant produce. High dietary fibre content plays an important role in human health.
Fat	Soxhlet method Principle: The technique involves extracting lipids in foods using an organic solvent (petroleum ether). It relies on the principle that the desired component is soluble in the organic solvent at a high temperature.
Protein	Kjeldahl method of protein analysis Principle: A food product is digested with a strong acid so that it releases nitrogen which can be determined by a suitable titration technique. The amount of protein present is then calculated from the nitrogen concentration of the food.

Carbohydrates	<p>Phenol-sulphuric acid method</p> <p>Principle: Carbohydrates are dehydrated by reaction with concentrated sulfuric acid to produce furfural derivatives. Further reaction between these derivatives and phenol gives off a detectable colour. This colour is quantified using spectrophotometry measurement.</p>
Iron and zinc	<p>Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS)</p> <p>Principle: Liquefied sample is aspirated, aerolized and mixed with combustible gases such as acetylene and air or acetylene and nitrous oxide and burned in a flame to atomize the minerals. Absorption spectroscopy is then used to quantify the different minerals, with reading for different minerals determined at different wavelengths.</p>
Carotenoids	<p>Spectrophotometry</p> <p>Principle: Carotenoids are extracted using acetone are quantified using UV spectrophotometry at 450 nm.</p>
Total phenolic compounds	<p>Using Folin-Ciocalteu assay in alkaline atmosphere</p> <p>Principle: Phenolic compounds are extracted using alcohol solution and reacted with Folin- Ciocalteu solution to coloured form compounds which are quantified using visible spectrophotometer at wavelength of 765 nm.</p>
Flavonoids	<p>Using the aluminium chloride colourimetric method</p> <p>Principle: Aluminium chloride is made to react with a C-4 keto groups and either the C-3 / C-5 hydroxyl groups of flavanols and flavones, forming stable complexes that are quantified using spectrophotometry at 510 nm.</p>
Total antioxidants	<p>Free radical scavenging assay by use of 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH)</p> <p>Principle: Relies on reduction of ferric-tripyridyl triazine complex to ferrous – tripyridyl triazine by the antioxidants of sample at low pH.</p>
Total condensed tannins	<p>Spectrophotometry</p> <p>Principle: The method entails reaction of condensed tannins with vanillin solution to produce coloured compounds which are quantified at 500 nm.</p>

4. Definitions and abbreviations

N/A

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

N/A

5.2. Equipment, instruments

Analysis	5.1 Solutions, standards, reagents, and reference material,	5.2 Equipment, Instruments
Moisture	None	Hot air oven (Gallenkamp, UK)
Ash	None	Muffle furnace (Mustek Limited, UK)
Dietary fibre	Acid detergent fibre, distilled water	Fibre analyzer (Labconco, Uk), 600 mL conical flask, glass sinter crucible, vacuum pump (Charles Austen pumps ltd, UK), Hot air oven (Gallenkamp, UK)
Fat	Petroleum ether	Soxhlet machine, Hot air oven (Gallenkamp, UK), fibre thimbles, fat crucibles, timer
Protein	Kjeldahl catalyst, concentrated Sulphuric acid, distilled water, phenolphthalein indicator, sodium hydroxide solution, boric acid, standard 0.05M hydrochloric acid,	Fume hood, 50 mL volumetric flasks, steam distillation unit, spectrophotometer.
Carbohydrates	Distilled water, lead acetate, concentrated Hydrochloric acid, Sodium Hydrogen Carbonate, 5% phenol solution, concentrated Sulphuric acid,	Conical flasks, 100 mL volumetric flasks, falcon tube, Centrifuge, vortex, spectrophotometer (Spectroquant® pharo 300).
Iron and Zinc	deionized water, nitric acid, distilled water,	Atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS)
Carotenoids	Acetone, petroleum ether, anhydrous sodium sulphate	50 mL volumetric flasks, separating funnel, motor and pestle, glass wool, funnels, spectrophotometer (Spectroquant® pharo 300).
Total phenolic compounds	80% methanol solution, Folin-Ciocalteu solution, sodium bicarbonate (10 % solution), distilled water.	Ultrasonicator (Bransonic series, M 2800-E; Branson Ultrasonics Co, Danbury, CT), timer, centrifuge (Heraeus megafuge 8 centrifuge),

		freezer, vortex, spectrophotometer (Spectroquant® pharo 300), test tubes, pipettes.
Flavanoids	80% methanol solution, distilled water, 5 % sodium nitrite solution, 10% Aluminium chloride, 1 M sodium hydroxide.	Ultrasonicator (Bransonic series, M 2800-E; Branson Ultrasonics Co, Danbury, CT), timer, centrifuge (Heraeus megafuge 8 centrifuge), freezer, vortex, spectrophotometer (Spectroquant® pharo 300), testtubes, pipettes.
Total antioxidants	80% methanol solution, distilled water, 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) solution.	Ultrasonicator (Bransonic series, M 2800-E; Branson Ultrasonics Co, Danbury, CT), timer, centrifuge (Heraeus megafuge 8 centrifuge), freezer, vortex, spectrophotometer (Spectroquant® pharo 300), testtubes, pipettes.
Total condensed tannins	80% methanol solution, distilled water, vanillin solution (4%) w/v, concentrated HCl.	Ultrasonicator (Bransonic series, M 2800-E; Branson Ultrasonics Co, Danbury, CT), timer, centrifuge (Heraeus megafuge 8 centrifuge), freezer, vortex, spectrophotometer (Spectroquant® pharo 300), test tubes, pipettes.

5.3. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

Lab coat, closed shoes, head gear, gloves and nose masks. These are used for mitigating risks and managing accidents in case of occurrence. Accidents like spillage of corrosive chemicals will not get in contact with the body.

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

For moisture content, ash, dietary fibre, fat, protein, carbohydrates, carotenoids no sample preparation is required prior to analysis.

For phytochemical analysis, phytochemical compounds were extracted using alcohol solutions as described by Hasan et al., (2022) and Natukunda et al., (2016) with slight modifications. Briefly, the homogeneous sample (1.0 g) was dissolved in 10 mL of 80% methanol (sample: solvent = 1:10 (w/v)). The falcon tube containing the mixture was suspended in ultrasonic water (Bransonic series, M 2800-E; Branson Ultrasonics Co, Danbury, CT) and subjected to ultrasonic treatment for 20 min at room temperature. The extract was immediately cooled at 4°C in a freezer for 10 min and then centrifuged at 4500 g for 5 min using a centrifuge (Heraeus megafuge 8 centrifuge). The supernatant was collected into a separate tube and stored at 4°C. The residue was then further re-extracted under the conditions previously described to ensure efficient extraction. The two supernatants were pooled in an airtight container and stored in a freezer at 4°C to be used in the determination of total phenolics content (TPC), total antioxidant activity (TAA), total flavonoid contents (TFC) and total condensed tannins (TCT) (Natukunda et al., 2016).

6.2. Analysis

Moisture content determination

Moisture content was determined using AOAC official method 919.38 (AOAC, 2016). About 10 g of sample was weighed onto a pre-conditioned and weighed petri-dish and dried in a hot air oven (Gallenkamp, UK) at 100°C for 16 hours. Dry sample was cooled in a desiccator for about 5 minutes and weighed. The percentage moisture content was calculated using the equation below.

$$\text{Moisture content (\%)} = \frac{W_2 - W_3}{W_2 - W_1} * 100$$

Where, W_1 = weight of empty dish, W_2 = weight of wet sample and dish; W_3 = weight of dry sample and dish.

Ash content determination

The determination of the ash content was done according to AOAC Official method 942.05 procedure. About 3 g of sample was weighed and ashed in an ignited muffle furnace (Mustek Limited, UK) at 550°C for 6 h as recommended by AOAC (1996). The ash crucible was then cooled in a desiccator for 10 minutes and weighed (Gressler *et al.*, 2010). Ash content was calculated as a percentage of the total sample weight using the equation below.

$$\text{Ash content (\%)} = \frac{W_3 - W_1}{W_2 - W_1} * 100$$

Where, W_1 = weight of crucible; W_2 = weight of sample and crucible; W_3 = weight of ash and crucible after ashing sample.

Dietary fibre determination

Dietary fibre of food matrix was determined using the method described by Kirk & Sawyer (1991). About 1 g of the sample was weighed out in duplicate into a 600 mL conical flask, 100 mL of acid detergent fibre was added and boiled for one hour in fibre analyzer (Labconco, UK). The digest was filtered through glass sinter crucible connected to a vacuum pump (Charles Austen pumps Ltd, UK) to collect the residues which were then be taken to the oven for drying at 100°C for 45 min to drive off the moisture (Schweizer, 1985). Dietary fibre was then calculated using equation below.

$$\text{Dietary fibre} = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_s} * 100$$

Where, W_1 = Weight of dry sinter-glass and sample (g), W_2 = Weight of dry sinter-glass (g) and W_s = Weight of the sample

Fat content determination

The fat in samples was determined using the Soxhlet method AOAC (2016). Briefly, 3 g of sample was weighed into a cellulose thimble and plugged with cotton wool. The thimble support holder was used to insert the thimble into the extraction unit, and the cup holder used to insert the extraction cup containing 50 mL of petroleum ether. The extraction process involved three stages, that is, boiling (25 minutes), rinsing (50 minutes) and recovery (10 minutes). The metallic dishes containing the extracted fat was dried in an oven at 100°C for 1 hour, then cooled in a desiccator and weighed. The fat content was determined from the equation below.

$$\% \text{ Crude fat} = \frac{F - T}{S} \times 100$$

Where, F is weight of beaker plus fat residue, T is weight of empty beaker, S is weight of original sample.

Protein determination

The protein content was determined using the Kjeldahl method (AOAC, 2002). Briefly, 0.5 g of the sample was weighed into numbered Kjeldahl micro-tubes to which 1 spatula-end full of Kjeldahl catalyst was added, followed by approximately 10 mL of concentrated Sulphuric acid. The contents of the tubes were digested in a fume hood until the digest cleared. After digestion, 30 mL of distilled water was added to the tubes and left to cool. The contents of the tubes were transferred into 50 mL volumetric flasks and the volume made up to the mark with distilled water. Pphenolphthalein indicator (3 drops) and 7 mL of 40% (w/w) sodium hydroxide solution were added to the 5 mL of digest in the steam distillation unit to evolve ammonia, which was tapped in

boric acid containing methyl red and bromocresol indicator. The boric acid receiving the solution was titrated with standard 0.05M hydrochloric acid to a red end point. The amount of hydrochloric acid used for titration was recorded. A reagent blank was also run-in order to determine the nitrogen in the reagents. The crude protein content was then determined using the equations below.

$$\text{Kjeldahl nitrogen (\%)} = \frac{(V_S - V_B) \times M \times 14.01 \times 50}{W \times 10 \times 5}$$

$$\text{Crude Protein} = \% \text{Kjeldahl N} \times F$$

Where V_S = volume of standardized acid used to titrate the digest, V_B = volume of standardized acid used to titrate reagent blank, M = molarity of standardized HCl, 14.01 is the atomic weight of nitrogen, W = the original weight of the sample, 10 = the factor to convert mg/g to percent, and F = factor to convert N to protein.

Carbohydrates determination

Carbohydrates content was determined using phenol-sulphuric acid method (Neilsen, 2009). Briefly, about 0.5 g of sample homogeneous sample was weighed in triplicate into conical flasks. About 50 mL of distilled water was added, followed by 1 mL of lead acetate and 1 mL of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The flasks were boiled on hot plate for 45 minutes, cooled to 80 °C and incubated at this temperature for 45 minutes. The mixture was cooled, sodium hydrogen carbonate was added to neutralize the excess acetate until effervescence stopped. The mixture was quantitatively transferred into 100 mL volumetric flask and topped up to mark with distilled water. A portion (50 mL) of the mixture was transferred into a falcon tube. The mixture was centrifuged at 4500 RPM for 5 minutes. A portion (10 mL) of the supernatant was pipetted into a clean 100 mL volumetric flask and topped up to mark with distilled water. For colour development, 0.1 mL of sample was pipetted into a clean dry test tube, 0.9 mL of distilled water was added followed by 1 mL of 5% phenol solution and 5 mL of concentrated sulphuric acid and the mixture was vortexed. A blank was prepared. The test tubes containing mixture were allowed to rest for 10 minutes followed by reading absorbance at 490 nm using a spectrophotometer (Spectroquant® pharo 300). The carbohydrate content was calculated using the equation below.

$$\text{Concentration (g/100 g)} = \frac{\text{Concentration (mg/mL)} \times \text{Final volume} \times \text{total volume} \times 100}{\text{Sample weight} \times \text{volume pipetted} \times 1000}$$

Carotenoids determination

Analysis of beta carotene was done using the HarvestPlus method (Tiony & Irene, 2021). This is described below.

Extraction process: About 0.5 g of sample was weighed, ground in mortar and pestle with some portion of cold Acetone. The mixture was filtered through glass wool on funnel into 50 mL volumetric flask. The process was repeated with small amounts of acetone portions until 50 mL mark was reached and the residue was free of colour. Partitioning: About 30-40 mL of petroleum ether (PE) was poured into the separating funnel and the acetone-carotenoid extract was added. Rinsing was done using 250 mL portion of distilled water while letting it flow along the walls of the funnel to avoid formation of an emulsion. The funnel was left to stand for the two phases to separate. The lower aqueous-acetone phase was discarded off. The rinsing was repeated with 250 mL portion of distilled water 3 times to remove residual acetone (total volume of 1 litre distilled water was used in this process).

The PE phase was passed through funnel with pad of glass wool and about 10 g of anhydrous sodium sulphate into a clean dry 50 mL volumetric flask. The filtrate was made to mark with PE. The extract was kept in a dark place prior to reading absorbance at wavelength 450 nm using a spectrophotometer. The concentration of carotenoid was calculated using the equation below.

$$\text{Carotenoid concentration } (\mu\text{g/g}) = \frac{\text{Absorbance} * \text{total volume} * 10000}{\text{sample weight} * 2592}$$

Where, 2592 = β -carotene Extinction Coefficient in petroleum ether.

Mineral analysis determination for Iron and Zinc

Atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS) was used to determine the concentration of iron and zinc in samples (Paul et al., 2016). The sample was collected in clean glassware that had been washed with acid and rinsed with deionized water prior to sample collection. The solid sample was dissolved in acid (nitric acid). Digestion temperature was set at 400°C. After digestion, the sample was filtered thorough glass filter and volume is made up to 100 mL with water.

The sample solution was aspirated into the spray chamber through capillary tube. The liquid sample was aerolized and mixed with combustible gases acetylene and air in the spray chamber and burned in a flame (2100 to 2800 °C) and the individual atoms of the sample was released to form a cloud inside the flame. The atoms of the element are released. To bring it from ground state into an excited state by passing UV light was required through hollow cathode lamp. On absorbing UV light at specific wavelengths, the ground state metal atoms were transitioned to higher electronic state thus reducing its intensity. The instrument measured the change in intensity. The region of the spectrum to be measured was selected by a monochromator. The isolated spectral line falls on the photomultiplier, the detector and the output were amplified and

sent to a readout device meter, digital or analogue or through a computer data processing system. The data was processed through software. Absorption of a selected wavelength was measured by the change in light intensity striking the photomultiplier detector and is directly related to the amount of element in the sample.

Determination of total phenolic compounds

The total phenolic content was determined by Folin-Ciocalteu assay (Hasan et al., 2022) with some modification. A 500 μ L of samples extract was mixed with 500 μ L Folin- Ciocalteu solution, then 1 mL sodium bicarbonate (10 % solution) was added to the mixture and finally adjusted to the mark with distilled water to make 10 mL solution. Then, the mixture was vortexed for a few seconds. The solutions were left for 35 min at room temperature in the dark place. Afterward, the absorbance was measured at 765 nm using UV–V is spectrophotometer (Spectroquant® pharo 300) (Waterhouse, 2002).

Determination of total flavonoid content

Total flavonoid content was measured using the colourimetric method described by (Islam et al., 2021) with some modifications. A portion (1 mL) of the extract was mixed with 4 mL of distilled water and 0.3 mL of 5 % sodium nitrite solution in 15 mL falcon tubes. Then, the tubes were allowed to stand for 5 min and subsequently added 0.3 mL of 10% aluminium chloride to the mixture and again allowed to stand for further 1 min. Lastly, 2 mL of 1 M sodium hydroxide and 2.4 mL of distilled water were added and mixed thoroughly. After centrifugation for 5 min at 4500 rpm, the tubes were kept in the dark at room temperature for 40 min. Absorbance was then determined at 510 nm against a blank prepared in a similar manner by replacing the mixture with methanol. The total flavonoid content was calculated from a standard curve of quercetin and the results were expressed as mg of quercetin equivalent per gram of dry sample (mg QE/g DM).

Determination of total antioxidant activity

The total antioxidant activity of eggplant was determined using a free radical scavenging assay by use of 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) as the source of the free radicals with slight modification (Natukunda et al., 2016). Briefly, 50 μ L of the sample extract was added to 2.9 mL of freshly prepared 80% ethanol solution of 100 μ M DPPH. The mixture was vortexed and allowed to stand for 30 minutes in the dark at room temperature. Absorbance of the resulting mixture was measured at 515 nm, using spectrophotometer (Spectroquant® pharo 300) against a blank (80% ethanol). The free-radical scavenging activity of the eggplant was calculated as follows.)

$$DPPH \text{ scarvenging effect (\%)} = \left[1 - \left(\frac{\text{absorbance of sample}}{\text{absorbance of control}} \right) \right] * 100 \text{ -- --Equation (8)}$$

The antioxidant content was determined using a standard curve of ascorbic acid (0.1–8 µg/mL). The results were expressed as milligram vitamin C equivalents per 100 mL of eggplant (mg VCE/100 g of the eggplant).

Determination of total condensed tannins

Total condensed tannins were determined using the method described by (Sun et al. 1998) with slight modifications. Briefly, 1.5 mL of vanillin solution (4%) w/v was added to 50 µL of diluted juice (1:10 of juice to water v/v) or cookie extract in a test tube. Immediately, 0.75 mL of concentrated HCl was added and the mixture vortexed. The mixture was incubated at room temperature for 10 min to allow for colour development. Absorbance was read at 500 nm (Spectroquant® pharo 300) with water as a blank. A standard curve was developed using catechin standards of varying concentrations (0.02 to 0.06 mg/mL). Total condensed tannins values were expressed as mg catechin equivalent/100 mL of the juice and mg catechin equivalent/100 g of cookies (Natukunda et al., 2016).

6.3. Schematic of method

N/A

6.4. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

N/A

7. Control procedures

Experiments were carried out in triplicates to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy. Moisture, ash, dietary fibre and fat analysis, crucibles were preconditioned in hot air oven at 100°C for 1 hour and placed in desiccator to cool prior to analysis. All glassware was preconditioned in oven prior to use for analysis

8. Calculations and data analysis

Results computed and presented on dry matter basis.

Descriptive statistics (means) derived using Microsoft Excel. Means of different treatments compared by applying analysis of variance and Turkey's test using SPSS software.

9. References

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DETERMINATION OF PASTING PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITE FLOURS

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

John H. Muyonga, hmuyonga@yahoo.com

2. Purpose

To determine the pasting profile of flour in order to gain insights of the behaviour of the flour when cooked into a gruel. This has implications on the thickness (and therefore the acceptable maximum solids content) recorded at the different points of heating, which has a bearing to the nutrients supplied by the gruels. It also depicts stability of the gruel during cooling. This analysis determines the suitability of starch for a specific end use

3. Principle

The measurement is based on the fact that starch containing flours when heated in presence of water register changes in viscosity due to starch gelatinization. The rapid visco analyser method (RVA) technique entails monitoring gruel viscosity during heating, holding at constant temperature while hot and cooling. The RVA works on the principle of mimicking the cooking process of a flour when a suspension is subjected to a heat-hold-cool-hold temperature cycle.

4. Definitions and abbreviations

RVA - Rapid Visco Analyser

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

Tap water

5.2. Equipment, instruments

Rapid visco analyser model RVA 4500, Perten Instruments, Hägersten, Sweden

5.3. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

Analysts should wear lab coats, closed shoes and gloves to protect themselves from accidents.

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

N/A

6.2. Analysis

A Rapid Visco Analyzer (model RVA 4500, Perten Instruments, Hägersten, Sweden) connected to a personal computer equipped with the manufacturer's ThermoLine for Windows software for operations and data management was used to analyze the pasting profile of the composite flours using standard procedure. The heating and cooling cycle settings were: slurry (3.5g flour and 25 mL distilled water), which was held at 50 °C for 1 min, heated to 95 °C and held at this temperature for 10 min and finally cooled to 50 °C and held for 3 min. Mixing was done at a contact rate (160 rpm) and analysis was repeated twice.

6.3. Schematic of method

N/A

6.4. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

7. Control procedures

Analyses done in triplicate to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy. Equipment calibrated regularly.

8. Calculations and data analysis

Descriptive statistics (Averages) will be derived using Microsoft Excel. Statistical significance of calculated means will be calculated using SPSS software.

9. References

-AOAC. (2016). Official methods of analysis (Jr. Dr. George W. Latimer, Ed.; 20th ed.). AOAC INTERNATIONAL SUITE 300 2275 RESEARCH BLVD ROCKVILLE, MARYLAND 20850–3250, USA.

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DETERMINATION OF MYCOTOXINS IN CEREAL-BASED PRODUCTS

1. Purpose

Evaluate the content of mycotoxins (aflatoxins and ochratoxin A) in cereal-based products

2. Principle

Modified AOAC 991.31 and AOAC 2000.03 methods for the simultaneous determination of total aflatoxins (AFs), aflatoxin B1, and ochratoxin A (OTA) in cereal-based foods by RP-HPLC coupled with fluorescence detection. The AOAC 991.31 and AOAC 2000.03 methods were modified by changing sample preparation steps in the simultaneous determination of AFs and OTA. The same extraction process was used for both AF and OTA analysis.

The method is described by Gazioğlu & Kolak (2015).

3. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

3.1 Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

- *Analytical standards of total AFs (AFB1, AFB2, AFG1, and AFG2), OTA, R-Biopharm (Darmstadt, Germany)*
- *Potassium bromide (≥99 purity, 104907),*
- *HPLC grade acetonitrile (≥99.93%purity),*
- *HPLC grade methanol (≥99.9% purity), nitric acid (65% purity), and glacial acetic acid (100% purity)0.1% (v/v) formic acid*
- *Phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) prepared by dissolving PBS tablets (Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany) in distilled water*

Stock solutions that contained 1000 ng/mL total AFs (AFB1, AFB2, AFG1, and AFG2) and 1000 ng/mL OTA were prepared from the purchased AF and OTA certified standards. The working standard solutions were prepared by diluting these stock solutions with methanol or methanol–water (60 + 40, v/v) to achieve different concentrations of mycotoxin mixtures. The calibration curve ranged from 0.08 to 10.00 ng/mL for total AFs and from 0.125 to 10.00 ng/mL for OTA. All

prepared solutions were stored at -4°C and kept at room temperature in the dark for 30 min before their use.

3.2 Equipment, instruments

- *Aflaprep and Ochraprep immunoaffinity Columns - R-Biopharm (Darmstadt, Germany)*
- *Shimadzu LC-20AT liquid chromatographic system (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) equipped with a fluorescence detector (RF-20A), autosampler system (SIL-20A), pump (LC-20AT), and column oven (CTO-10AS) and controlled by Lab Solutions software*
- *RP C18 column Cronusil-S ODS2 (4.6 × 250 mm, 100 Å, and 5 μm particle size; Gloucester, UK)*
- *KOBRA Cell electrochemical postcolumn derivatization system (R-Biopharm)*

3.3 Health and Safety and personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

AFs and OTA are toxic substances; therefore, were always manipulated in solution, avoiding the formation of dust and aerosols. Nitrile gloves were used for all procedures

4. Procedures

4.1 Sample preparation

For Blank wheat samples were spiked with a suitable amount of mycotoxins to achieve 6.0 and 8.0 μg/kg total AFs, and 3.0 and 8.0 μg/kg OTA. After 30 min at room temperature, the spiked samples were extracted, cleaned up, and analyzed using the modified AOAC 991.31 and AOAC 2000.03 methods. All samples were ground with a blender. Each ground and spiked sample (25 g) was extracted with 125 mL methanol (75%). After blending vigorously for 30 min, the extract was filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper. For AF analysis, 15 mL filtrate was diluted with 30 mL distilled water and 15 mL of the supernatant was passed through an immunoaffinity column without preconditioning. For OTA analysis, 5 mL of the filtrate was diluted with 40 mL distilled water and 45 mL of the supernatant was passed through an immunoaffinity column without preconditioning. After the sample passed, the column was washed with 10 mL distilled water. Then, the column was air-dried and AFs were eluted with 1 mL methanol and OTA eluted with 1.5 mL of methanol–acetic acid (98 + 2, v/v). Finally, 1 mL and 1.5 mL distilled water were added for AFs and OTA, respectively, into a glass vial, and 100 μL of these eluates was directly injected for HPLC.

4.2 Analysis

Acetonitrile–methanol–water for AFs, and methanol–water–acetic acid for OTA were used as mobile phases to equilibrate RP HPLC columns before analyses. The wavelengths of excitation and emission were 365 and 435 nm for AFs, and 333 and 460 nm for OTA, respectively. The injection volume was 100 μL, and flow rate was 1.00 mL/min. Separation was achieved at 30°C under isocratic elution with the following mobile phases: acetonitrile–methanol–water (8 + 38 +

54, v/v/v) with 0.2 g/L potassium bromide, acidified with nitric acid (300 µL/L, 65%) for AF analysis and methanol–water–acetic acid (68.5 + 29 + 2.5, v/v/v) for OTA analysis.

5. Control procedures

A cereal sample not contaminated with mycotoxins was used as a blank sample for spiking.

Analyses of replicate spiked samples provided applicability and verification of the method.

6. Calculations and data analysis

The calculated and expected concentrations (C) of the spiked sample were compared to determine the recovery values using following equation:

$$\text{Recovery, \%} = [C_{\text{spiked sample}}/C_{\text{expected}}] \times 100$$

Results are expressed in µg kg⁻¹.

7. References

49.2.18 AOAC Official Method 991.31 Aflatoxins in Corn, Raw Peanuts, and Peanut Butter: Immunoaffinity Column (Aflatest) Method, <https://doi.org/10.1093/9780197610145.003.3973>

49.6.04 AOAC Official Method 2000.03 Ochratoxin A in Barley: Immunoaffinity Column HPLC, <https://doi.org/10.1093/9780197610145.003.4008>

Gazioğlu, I., & Kolak, U. (2015). Method validation for the quantitative analysis of aflatoxins (B1, B2, G1, and G2) and ochratoxin A in processed cereal-based foods by HPLC with fluorescence detection. *Journal of AOAC International*, 98(4), 939-945.

2.4.2. Snacks from novel local varieties/species: orange fleshed sweet potatoes, grain amaranth, and pumpkin (prototype n. 20)

DETERMINATION OF SENSORY ACCEPTANCE OF BAKED SNACK FROM COMPOSITE FLOURS

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

John H. Muyonga, hmuyonga@yahoo.com

2. Purpose

To determine the sensory perceptions of baked snacks (daddies) from composite flours, in order to determine commercialization potential of the nutritious products.

3. Principle

Sensory analysis by a small panel (of at least 30) provides insights on the potential consumer acceptance of food products.

4. Definitions and abbreviations

N/A

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

No solutions, reagents or reference materials required

5.2. Equipment, instruments

None

5.3. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

Approximately 50 g of each sample given to each analyst on disposable plates.

6.2. Analysis

Analysis was done using 9-point hedonic scale following the procedure as described by the Food & Drink Federation. <https://egyankosh.ac.in/bitstream/123456789/11521/1/Experiment-10.pdf>

6.3. Schematic of method

N/A

6.4. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

N/A

7. Control procedures

Analyses done in triplicate to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy. Equipment calibrated regularly.

Analysts were put in separate compartments during testing. They were also provided with water for mouth rinsing between tests for different samples. Tests were scheduled for 10-11 am, a time at which panelists were expected not to be very hungry or very satisfied.

8. Calculations and data analysis

Descriptive statistics (averages) will be derived using Microsoft Excel. Statistical significance of calculated means will be calculated using SPSS software.

9. References

Food & Drink Federation.

<https://www.fdfscotland.org.uk/globalassets/resources/toolkits/reformulation-support-toolkit/sensory-analysis-guide-interactive.pdf>. Accessed February 2024.

DETERMINATION OF ACRYLAMIDE IN FOOD PRODUCTS

8. Purpose

Evaluate the content of acrylamide in cereal based products

9. Principle

Acrylamide is extracted and purified by SPE and then analysed by LC-ESI-MS/MS in positive ion mode (ESI⁺).

10. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

10.1 Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

- *Internal standard solution (¹³C₃-labelled acrylamide in MeOH)*
- *0.1% (v/v) formic acid*
- *Methanol (99.5/0.5, v/v)*
- *Stock solution of acrylamide with water in the 1.5–200 µg/L range*

10.2 Equipment, instruments

- *Agilent 6420 triple quadrupole (Agilent, Santa Clara, United States)*
- *Agilent 1290 Infinity LC Pump equipped with an autosampler and a thermostated column oven*

10.3 Health and Safety and personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

Acrylamide is a known carcinogen and genotoxicant, meaning it can damage DNA and potentially lead to cancer. Proper measures need to be undertaken when managing the analytical standard.

4. Procedures

11.1 Sample preparation

Food samples were finely ground before the extraction.

11.2 Analysis

1 g of sample was weighted into a polypropylene conical tube, and 100 µL 10µg/mL internal standard solution (¹³C₃-labelled acrylamide in MeOH) followed by 10 mL 0.1% (v/v) formic acid were added. After mixing with Vortex for 10 min, the extract was centrifuged at 4500 rpm for 15 min. A 2 mL portion of clarified solution was removed, avoiding collection of top oil layer when present, and filtered through paper filter. A solid-phase extraction (SPE) was performed using C18 cartridges (1000 mg, 6 mL; Phenomenex). Cartridges were first conditioned with 5 mL methanol followed by 5 mL water; 1 mL of filtered sample was loaded and washed with 1 mL water. Elution was performed with 1 mL acetone. Acetone was removed under nitrogen flow and sample was dissolved in 1 mL 0.1% (v/v) formic acid before injection. SPE clean-up was performed on 3 extracts for each sample.

HPLC-ESI-MS/MS analysis. LC-ESI-MS/MS in positive ion mode (ESI⁺) analyses were performed by an Agilent 6420 triple quadrupole (Agilent, Santa Clara, United States) coupled to an Agilent 1290 Infinity LC Pump equipped with an autosampler and a thermostated column oven, according to Calbiani, Careri, Elviri, Mangia, and Zagnoni (2004) with some modifications. The analytical column was a Poroshell 120 C18, 3.0×100 mm, 2.7 µm (Agilent, USA) maintained at 20 °C. The elution was in isocratic mode using a mixture of 0.1% (v/v) aqueous formic acid and methanol (99.5/0.5, v/v) as mobile phase at a flow rate of 0.3 mL/min. The sample injection

volume was 10 μL . Full-scan analyses were performed in the 40–100 Da mass range, acquiring the following transitions: extracted ion at m/z 55, due to the transition $72 > 55$, and at m/z 58, due to the transition $75 > 58$ were used for the quantitative analysis. A calibration curve was made for the quantification diluting stock solution of acrylamide with water in the 1.5–200 $\mu\text{g/L}$ range. For acquisition and processing data, the Agilent MassHunter Workstation software was used.

12. Control procedures

All analytical determinations need to be carried out in triplicate to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

13. Calculations and data analysis

A calibration curve was made for the quantification diluting stock solution of acrylamide with water in the 1.5–200 $\mu\text{g/L}$ range. For acquisition and processing data, the Agilent MassHunter Workstation software was used.

Results are expressed in mg kg^{-1} of dry weight.

14. References

*Calbiani, F., Careri, M., Elviri, L., Mangia, A., & Zagnoni, I. (2004). Development and single-laboratory validation of a reversed-phase liquid chromatography-electrospray tandem mass spectrometry method for identification and determination of acrylamide in foods. *Journal of AOAC International*, 87(1), 107–115.*

2.5. UoM

2.5.1. Composite flours with novel local varieties: moringa and teff (prototype n. 13)

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Gebreyohannes Girmay, UoM, gebreyohannes.girmay@gmail.com

2. Purpose

The aim of the analyses is detailing the basic physico-chemical and nutrient contents; detection of pathogenic micro-organisms; and sensory analysis of the users. The analysis of moisture content indicates the shelf life and susceptibility to microbial growth of the product.

3. Principle

The analysis of proteins indicates the nutritional value and functional properties of the product. The analysis of fats indicates to energy content, flavour, & shelf life; Carbohydrates indicates to energy & includes starch & sugars; and dietary fibre to digestive health. Ash content indicates total mineral content.

Minerals: Calcium indicates to bone health; Iron to blood oxygen transport; Magnesium indicates to muscle & nerve function. Zinc indicates to immune function & enzyme activity; and Potassium indicates to maintaining fluid & electrolyte balance.

Vitamins: Vitamin A Important for vision & immune function immune function. B Vitamins (B1, B2, B3, B6, B12) indicates energy metabolism. Vitamin C indicates immune function & antioxidant properties. Vitamin E- indicates to antioxidant that protects cells from oxidative damage.

Anti-nutritional factors like phytates, tannins, and trypsin inhibitors indicate to nutrient absorption.

Mycotoxins indicate to toxic compounds produced by fungi that can contaminate grains.

The official methods of Association of Analytical Chemists (AOAC) will be used throughout the laboratory analysis of teff-Moringa blended flowers.

4. Definitions and abbreviations

N/A

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

N/A

5.2. Equipment, instruments

N/A

5.3. Health and Safety and personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

N/A

6. Procedures

The teff and moringa samples are collected from the precision harvesting plots of the Laelay Machew / Axum –Ethiopia food hub in January 2024. The sub-samples of teff and Moringa are ground to pass a 1mm sieve in the UoM Laboratory and stored and readied for subsequent analyses. The teff flour and Moringa powder were blended according to the protocol prepared in 2023 for the blending treatments. The blended flour is currently being prepared and get ready to be for analyses in UoM to be continued during this July and August 2024.

A detailed description of the steps and procedures to be performed are indicated in Table 2.5.1.1. Each procedure will be produced in enough copies for the laboratory personnel will follow the steps during the analysis. Most of the analyses are to be carried out in UoM laboratories and some of the parameters will be carried out in Addis Ababa University, Ethiopia. The details of the methods are given in table 1 below.

Table 2.5.1.1. Nutritional Analysis methods (blended & pure samples)

S.N	Nutritional components	Standard methods
1	Moisture	Oven drying method at 65°C until a constant weight is achieved.

		(AOAC Official Method 934.01)
2	Protein	Kjeldahl method or Dumas combustion method (Kjeldahl: AOAC Official Method 988.05) (Dumas: AOAC Official Method 992.15)
3	Amino Acid Profiles	HPLC after acid hydrolysis (AOAC Official Method 994.12)
4	Fats	Soxhlet extraction method (AOAC Official Method 945.38)
5	Fatty Acid Profiles	Gas chromatography (GC) (AOAC Official Method 996.06)
6	Carbohydrate	Calculated by subtracting the sum of moisture, protein, fat, and ash content from 100%. (AOAC Official Method 986.25 for total carbohydrates.)
7	Dietary fibre	AOAC enzymatic-gravimetric methods. (AOAC Official Method 985.29)
8	Minerals	Atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS) or inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). - (AAS: AOAC Official Method 984.27) - (ICP-MS: AOAC Official Method 990.08)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Calcium • Iron • Magnesium • Zinc • Potassium 	
8	Vitamins	High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) or specific assays. - (Vitamin A: AOAC Official Method 974.29) - (B Vitamins: AOAC Official Methods 985.33 (B1), 970.65 (B2), 944.13 (B3), 961.15 (B6), 952.20 (B12)) - (Vitamin C: AOAC Official Method 967.21) - (Vitamin E: AOAC Official Method 992.03)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vitamin A • B Vitamins (B1, B2, B3, B6, B12) • Vitamin C • Vitamin E 	
9	Ash content	Muffle furnace method at 550°C. (AOAC Official Method 923.03)
10	Anti-Nutritional Factors	- Spectrophotometric & chromatographic methods. (Phytates: AOAC Official Method 986.11) (Tannins: AOAC Official Method 952.03) (Trypsin Inhibitors: AOAC Official Method 973.03)
11	Mycotoxins	Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) or HPLC.

		(ELISA: AOAC Official Method 2000.02) (HPLC: AOAC Official Method 999.07)
12	Heavy Metals	AAS or ICP-MS. (AAS: AOAC Official Method 999.10) (ICP-MS: AOAC Official Method 2011.19)

7. Control procedures

To ensure reproducibility All the samples will be done in triplicates of analysis. Quality checks will employ random control samples in every 15 samples in the array of the samples to be analyzed.

8. Calculations and data analysis

N/A

9. References

- Moisture Content: AOAC International. (2005). Official Methods of Analysis of AOAC International Method 934.01.
- Protein Content: AOAC International. (2005). Official Methods of Analysis of AOAC International. Methods 988.05 and 992.15.
- Fat Content: AOAC International. (2005). Official Methods of Analysis of AOAC International. Method 945.38.
- Carbohydrate Content: AOAC International. (2005). Official Methods of Analysis of AOAC International. Method 986.25.
- Dietary Fibre: AOAC International. (2005). Official Methods of Analysis of AOAC International. Method 985.29.
- Calcium, Iron, Magnesium, Zinc, Potassium: AOAC International. (2005). Official Methods of Analysis of AOAC International. Methods 984.27 and 990.08.
- Vitamin A: AOAC International. (2005). Official Methods of Analysis of AOAC International. Method 974.29.
- B Vitamins: AOAC International. (2005). Official Methods of Analysis of AOAC International. Methods 985.33, 970.65, 944.13, 961.15, 952.20.
- Vitamin C: AOAC International. (2005). Official Methods of Analysis of AOAC International. Method 967.21.
- Vitamin E: AOAC International. (2005). Official Methods of Analysis of AOAC International. Method 992.03.
- Ash Content: AOAC International. (2005). Official Methods of Analysis of AOAC International. Method 923.03.
- Phytates: AOAC International. (2005). Official Methods of Analysis of AOAC International. Method 986.11.

- Tannins: AOAC International. (2005). Official Methods of Analysis of AOAC International. Method 952.03.
- Trypsin Inhibitors: AOAC International. (2005). Official Methods of Analysis of AOAC International. Method 973.03.
- ELISA: AOAC International. (2005). Official Methods of Analysis of AOAC International. Method 2000.02.
- HPLC: AOAC International. (2005). Official Methods of Analysis of AOAC International. Method 999.07.
- AAS: AOAC International. (2005). Official Methods of Analysis of AOAC International. Method 999.10.
- ICP-MS: AOAC International. (2005). Official Methods of Analysis of AOAC International. Method 2011.19.

DETERMINATION OF MYCOTOXINS IN CEREAL-BASED PRODUCTS

1. Purpose

Evaluate the content of mycotoxins (aflatoxins and ochratoxin A) in cereal-based products

2. Principle

Modified AOAC 991.31 and AOAC 2000.03 methods for the simultaneous determination of total aflatoxins (AFs), aflatoxin B1, and ochratoxin A (OTA) in cereal-based foods by RP-HPLC coupled with fluorescence detection. The AOAC 991.31 and AOAC 2000.03 methods were modified by changing sample preparation steps in the simultaneous determination of AFs and OTA. The same extraction process was used for both AF and OTA analysis.

The method is described by Gazioglu & Kolak (2015).

3. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

3.1 Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

- *Analytical standards of total AFs (AFB1, AFB2, AFG1, and AFG2), OTA, R-Biopharm (Darmstadt, Germany)*
- *Potassium bromide (≥99 purity, 104907),*
- *HPLC grade acetonitrile (≥99.93%purity),*
- *HPLC grade methanol (≥99.9% purity), nitric acid (65% purity), and glacial acetic acid (100% purity)0.1% (v/v) formic acid*
- *Phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) prepared by dissolving PBS tablets (Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany) in distilled water*

Stock solutions that contained 1000 ng/mL total AFs (AFB1, AFB2, AFG1, and AFG2) and 1000 ng/mL OTA were prepared from the purchased AF and OTA certified standards. The working standard solutions were prepared by diluting these stock solutions with methanol or methanol–

water (60 + 40, v/v) to achieve different concentrations of mycotoxin mixtures. The calibration curve ranged from 0.08 to 10.00 ng/mL for total AFs and from 0.125 to 10.00 ng/mL for OTA. All prepared solutions were stored at -4°C and kept at room temperature in the dark for 30 min before their use.

3.2 Equipment, instruments

- Aflaprep and Ochraprep immunoaffinity Columns - R-Biopharm (Darmstadt, Germany)
- Shimadzu LC-20AT liquid chromatographic system (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) equipped with a fluorescence detector (RF-20A), autosampler system (SIL-20A), pump (LC-20AT), and column oven (CTO-10AS) and controlled by Lab Solutions software
- RP C18 column Cronusil-S ODS2 (4.6 × 250 mm, 100 Å, and 5 µm particle size; Gloucester, UK)
- KOBRA Cell electrochemical postcolumn derivatization system (R-Biopharm)

3.3 Health and Safety and personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

AFs and OTA are toxic substances; therefore, were always manipulated in solution, avoiding the formation of dust and aerosols. Nitrile gloves were used for all procedures

4. Procedures

4.1 Sample preparation

For Blank wheat samples were spiked with a suitable amount of mycotoxins to achieve 6.0 and 8.0 µg/kg total AFs, and 3.0 and 8.0 µg/kg OTA. After 30 min at room temperature, the spiked samples were extracted, cleaned up, and analyzed using the modified AOAC 991.31 and AOAC 2000.03 methods. All samples were ground with a blender. Each ground and spiked sample (25 g) was extracted with 125 mL methanol (75%). After blending vigorously for 30 min, the extract was filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper. For AF analysis, 15 mL filtrate was diluted with 30 mL distilled water and 15 mL of the supernatant was passed through an immunoaffinity column without preconditioning. For OTA analysis, 5 mL of the filtrate was diluted with 40 mL distilled water and 45 mL of the supernatant was passed through an immunoaffinity column without preconditioning. After the sample passed, the column was washed with 10 mL distilled water. Then, the column was air-dried and AFs were eluted with 1 mL methanol and OTA eluted with 1.5 mL of methanol–acetic acid (98 + 2, v/v). Finally, 1 mL and 1.5 mL distilled water were added for AFs and OTA, respectively, into a glass vial, and 100 µL of these eluates was directly injected for HPLC.

4.2 Analysis

Acetonitrile–methanol–water for AFs, and methanol–water–acetic acid for OTA were used as mobile phases to equilibrate RP HPLC columns before analyses. The wavelengths of excitation and emission were 365 and 435 nm for AFs, and 333 and 460 nm for OTA, respectively. The injection volume was 100 µL, and flow rate was 1.00 mL/min. Separation was achieved at 30°C

under isocratic elution with the following mobile phases: acetonitrile–methanol–water (8 + 38 + 54, v/v/v) with 0.2 g/L potassium bromide, acidified with nitric acid (300 µL/L, 65%) for AF analysis and methanol–water–acetic acid (68.5 + 29 + 2.5, v/v/v) for OTA analysis.

5. Control procedures

A cereal sample not contaminated with mycotoxins was used as a blank sample for spiking.

Analyses of replicate spiked samples provided applicability and verification of the method.

6. Calculations and data analysis

The calculated and expected concentrations (C) of the spiked sample were compared to determine the recovery values using following equation:

$$\text{Recovery, \%} = [C_{\text{spiked sample}}/C_{\text{expected}}] \times 100$$

Results are expressed in µg kg⁻¹.

7. References

49.2.18 AOAC Official Method 991.31 Aflatoxins in Corn, Raw Peanuts, and Peanut Butter: Immunoaffinity Column (Aflatest) Method, <https://doi.org/10.1093/9780197610145.003.3973>

49.6.04 AOAC Official Method 2000.03 Ochratoxin A in Barley: Immunoaffinity Column HPLC, <https://doi.org/10.1093/9780197610145.003.4008>

*Gazioğlu, I., & Kolak, U. (2015). Method validation for the quantitative analysis of aflatoxins (B1, B2, G1, and G2) and ochratoxin A in processed cereal-based foods by HPLC with fluorescence detection. *Journal of AOAC International*, 98(4), 939-945.*

2.6. UoN

2.6.1. Composite flours with novel local varieties: therapeutic powder for diabetic people (prototype n. 14)

CHARACTERIZATION OF COMMON TREE TOMATO FRUIT VARIETIES IN KENYA

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Prof. Michael W. Okoth, Department of Food Science Nutrition and Technology - University of Nairobi, mwokoth@uonbi.ac.ke

8. Purpose

The characterization aimed at analysing the attributes impacting therapeutic powder processing from tree tomato fruits varieties in Kenya to help in the selection of the best quality raw materials on a functional basis.

9. Principle

The therapeutic powder for diabetic people will be analysed for proximate composition, pH, Total soluble solids, Titratable Acidity, Vitamin C, Vitamin A, Total phenolic content, Flavonoid content, Antioxidant activity, Minerals content and sensory attributes to determine the functional properties and overall acceptability.

2. Product

Tree tomato (*Cyphomandra betacea*), also known as tamarillo, was the product selected.

Red and yellow Tree Tomato fruits and pulps from Kenya.

About 550 kg of mature firm-ripe tree tomato fruits were randomly procured from five different traders at Marigiti market in Nairobi, Kenya in September, 2023.

3. Method of analysis

Parameter	Method used
Proximate composition	AOAC (2010) methods: As per the specific test methods described (in bracket): Moisture content (920:151); crude fibre (2011.25); Crude protein (2001:11); Crude fat (996.06); Ash content (940:26).
pH	Omayio et al. 2022
Total soluble solids (°Brix)	Omayio et al. 2022
Titratable Acidity	AOAC method 942.15
Vitamin C	AOAC Method 967.21-1968
Vitamin A	AOAC method 992.06
Total phenolic content	Delouee and Urooj, 2007
Flavonoid content	Omayio et al. 2022
Antioxidant activity	Zacarías-García <i>et al.</i> 2021.
Minerals content	AOAC Method 2005.08

4. Control procedures

All analytical determinations were carried out in duplicate to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

5. References

- AOAC. 2010. Official Methods of Analysis: 18th Edition, 2005. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-9936\(90\)87098-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-9936(90)87098-7).
- Diep TT, Pook C, Yoo MJY. 2020a. Physicochemical properties and proximate composition of tamarillo (*Solanum betaceum* Cav.) fruits from New Zealand. *J Food Compos Anal.* 92:103563. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfca.2020.103563>.
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2.6.2. Therapeutic food: tamarillo juice for adults with diabetes (prototype n. 24)

CHARACTERIZATION OF EFFECT OF PULP EXTRACTION METHODS OF TREE TOMATO FRUIT VARIETIES IN KENYA

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Prof. Michael W. Okoth, Department of Food Science Nutrition and Technology - University of Nairobi, mwokoth@uonbi.ac.ke

2. Product

Pulp from the Red and Yellow Tree tomato (*Cyphomandra betacea*), also known as tamarillo, varieties from Kenya were the product selected.

About 300 kg of mature firm-ripe tree tomato fruits were randomly procured from five different traders at Marigiti market in Nairobi, Kenya in September 2023 then treated using cold water, Hot water and steam before extraction. The treatments for each tree tomato variety were not replicated.

3. Method of analysis

Parameter	Method used
Proximate composition	AOAC (2010) methods: As per the specific test methods described (in bracket): Moisture content (920:151); Crude fibre (2011.25); Crude protein (2001:11); Crude fat (996.06); Ash content (940:26).
pH	ISO 26323:2009(en)
Total soluble solids (oBrix)	ISO 2173:1978
Titratable Acidity	AOAC method 942.15
Vitamin C	AOAC Method 967.21-1968
Vitamin A	AOAC method 992.06
Total phenolic content	Delouee and Urooj, 2007
Flavonoid content	Omayio et al. 2022
Antioxidant activity	Zacarias-García <i>et al.</i> 2021.
Minerals content	AOAC Method 2005.08

4. Control procedures

All analytical determinations were carried out in duplicate to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

5. References

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CHARACTERIZATION OF THERAPEUTIC MIXED FRUIT JUICES

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Sophia Ngala, Department of Food science Nutrition and Technology - University of Nairobi, sngala@uonbi.ac.ke

2. Product

Pulp from the Red Tree tomato (*Cyphomandra betacea*), also known as tamarillo, from Kenya was the product selected to formulate a therapeutic mixed fruit juices.

About 1250 kg of mature firm-ripe tree tomato fruits were randomly procured from five different traders at Marigiti market in Nairobi, Kenya in December, 2023 then blanched before pulp extraction and formulation of fruit juices. Fruit juice production was not replicated.

3. Method of analysis

Parameter	Method used
Proximate composition	AOAC (2010) methods: As per the specific test methods described (in bracket): Moisture content (920:151); Crude fibre (2011.25); Crude protein (2001:11); Crude fat (996.06);

	Ash content (940:26).
Vitamin C	AOAC Method 967.21-1968
Microbial Analysis TVC, E.coli, Yeasts and molds)	ISO Methods ; AOAC, 1995;
-Total phenolic content	Delouee and Urooj, 2007
Flavonoid content	Omayio et al. 2022
Antioxidant activity	Zacarías-García <i>et al.</i> 2021.
Minerals content	AOAC Method 2005.08
Sensory Analysis	Lawless and Heymann (2010)

4. Control procedures

All analytical determinations were carried out in duplicate to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

5. References

- AOAC. 2010. Official Methods of Analysis: 18th Edition,2005. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-9936\(90\)87098-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-9936(90)87098-7).
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-Zacarias-García, J., Rey, F., Gil, J. V., Rodrigo, M. J., & Zacarias, L. (2021). Antioxidant capacity in fruit of Citrus cultivars with marked differences in pulp colouration: Contribution of carotenoids and vitamin C. Food Science and Technology International, 27(3), 210–222. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1082013220944018>

2.6.3. Snacks from novel local varieties/species: cereal-based snacks for children (prototype n. 23)

CHARACTERIZATION OF QUINOA SEEDS

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Dr. Dasel W.M. Kaindi, University of Nairobi, mulwa.dasel@students.uonbi.ac.ke

2. Product

QUINOA SEEDS: Quinoa is a pseudo-grain whose origin can be traced to South American Andes region (5000BC-3000BC) (Silva et al., 2020). It is well endowed with a wide variety of nutrients that include: protein, lipids, fibre, vitamins (B6, pantothenic acid, Biotin, Vitamin A and Folate) and minerals (iron, Calcium, zinc, potassium among others) as well as beneficial phyto-chemicals including saponins, and phytosterols. It is well known for its perfect balance of the essential amino acids (Tanwar, 2016). Agricultural experimental trials were done in the University of Nairobi, Upper Kabete Campus, Field Station between May 2022 and August 2022. Four varieties of quinoa namely Biobio, Cherry Vanilla, Titicaca and Brightest brilliant red (BBR) were grown. The plants utilized both rain and irrigation water during growth. After 3 months in the field, the matured seed was harvested, dried and cleaned ready for analysis in the laboratory. A sample of 15g from each variety was taken and subjected to proximate composition and mineral component analysis. The analysis was done in triplicates, this helps to minimize the experimental error.

3. Method of analysis

Two methods of analysis were used to characterize quinoa seeds. Proximate composition analysis and atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS). Proximate composition analysis determines moisture, crude protein, fat, ash, fibre, and carbohydrate content. Different methods and procedures were used to determine the amount of various elements as follows; Moisture was determined using air oven method; Fibre content was determined using acid/base digestion, ash content levels was determined using muffle furnace method, protein was determined using the Khedjal distillation

method; the Soxhlet method for fat determination and finally the amount of carbohydrate was determined using the difference method (AOAC, 2005)

The amounts of the different minerals were determined using atomic absorption spectroscopy, which is a technique that uses the principle; distinct elements will absorb the wavelengths differently. Atoms and ions can absorb light at a specific, and unique wavelength.

Proximate composition analysis methods.

Sno	ELEMENT	EQUIPMENT/ Instruments	PROCEDURE	CALCULATIONS	REFERENCES
1	Moisture (Air Oven Method)	Porcelain Dishes Air-Oven at 105°C Desiccator	As described in (AOAC, 2005)	The moisture content will then be expressed in percentage as follows; $W_1 - W_2 / W_1$ * 100 where W_1 is weight before drying and W_2 is weight after drying.	(AOAC, 2005)
3	Ash (Muffle Furnace Method)	Porcelain crucibles Bunsen Burner Muffle oven at 500°C	As described in (AOAC, 2005)	Total ash content = weight of the ash divided by the weight of the original sample multiplied by 100%.	(AOAC, 2005)
4	Protein (Kjeldahl Method)	Kjeldahl flasks Digestion and distillation units Conical flasks, 400 mL tubes Burette 50mL Pipetter 20mL	As described in (AOAC, 2005)	The amount of protein in the sample is determined by multiplying the total nitrogen content with a factor of 6.25	(AOAC, 2005)
5	Fat (Soxhlet Method)	Flat-bottomed flask 250mL Soxhlet extractors and condensers Extraction thimbles Rotary evaporator Air-oven at 105°C Desiccator	As described in (AOAC, 2005)	% fat = $(W_1 - W_2) / S \times 100$ W_1 - Weight of empty flask (g) Weight of flask and extracted fat (g) s - Weight of the quinoa sample	(AOAC, 2005)
6	Carbohydrate (The difference method)		As described in (AOAC, 2005)	% Carbohydrates = $100 - (\text{moisture content} +$	(AOAC, 2005)

				%ash+% fibre +%protein+%fat]	
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4. Control procedures

All analytical determinations were carried out in duplicate to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

5. References

- Silva, P. M., Massuela, D. C., Khan, M. W., Hamar, A., Khajehei, F., Grae, S., & Piatti, C. (2020). Quinoa (*Chenopodium quinoa* Willd.): An Overview of the Potentials of the “Golden Grain” and Socio-Economic and Environmental Aspects of Its Cultivation and Marketization. *Foods*, 9(216), 31.
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DETERMINATION OF MYCOTOXINS IN CEREAL-BASED PRODUCTS

3. Purpose

Evaluate the content of mycotoxins (aflatoxins and ochratoxin A) in cereal-based products

15.Principle

Modified AOAC 991.31 and AOAC 2000.03 methods for the simultaneous determination of total aflatoxins (AFs), aflatoxin B1, and ochratoxin A (OTA) in cereal-based foods by RP-HPLC coupled with fluorescence detection. The AOAC 991.31 and AOAC 2000.03 methods were modified by changing sample preparation steps in the simultaneous determination of AFs and OTA. The same extraction process was used for both AF and OTA analysis.

The method is described by Gazioglu & Kolak (2015).

16.Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

16.1 Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

- *Analytical standards of total AFs (AFB1, AFB2, AFG1, and AFG2), OTA, R-Biopharm (Darmstadt, Germany)*
- *Potassium bromide (≥99 purity, 104907),*

- HPLC grade acetonitrile ($\geq 99.93\%$ purity),
- HPLC grade methanol ($\geq 99.9\%$ purity), nitric acid (65% purity), and glacial acetic acid (100% purity)
- 0.1% (v/v) formic acid
- Phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) prepared by dissolving PBS tablets (Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany) in distilled water

Stock solutions that contained 1000 ng/mL total AFs (AFB1, AFB2, AFG1, and AFG2) and 1000 ng/mL OTA were prepared from the purchased AF and OTA certified standards. The working standard solutions were prepared by diluting these stock solutions with methanol or methanol-water (60 + 40, v/v) to achieve different concentrations of mycotoxin mixtures. The calibration curve ranged from 0.08 to 10.00 ng/mL for total AFs and from 0.125 to 10.00 ng/mL for OTA. All prepared solutions were stored at -4°C and kept at room temperature in the dark for 30 min before their use.

16.2 Equipment, instruments

- Aflaprep and Ochraprep immunoaffinity Columns - R-Biopharm (Darmstadt, Germany)
- Shimadzu LC-20AT liquid chromatographic system (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) equipped with a fluorescence detector (RF-20A), autosampler system (SIL-20A), pump (LC-20AT), and column oven (CTO-10AS) and controlled by Lab Solutions software
- RP C18 column Cronusil-S ODS2 (4.6 \times 250 mm, 100 Å, and 5 μm particle size; Gloucester, UK)
- KOBRA Cell electrochemical postcolumn derivatization system (R-Biopharm)

16.3 Health and Safety and personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

AFs and OTA are toxic substances; therefore, were always manipulated in solution, avoiding the formation of dust and aerosols. Nitrile gloves were used for all procedures

4. Procedures

17.1 Sample preparation

Blank wheat samples were spiked with a suitable amount of mycotoxins to achieve 6.0 and 8.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ total AFs, and 3.0 and 8.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ OTA. After 30 min at room temperature, the spiked samples were extracted, cleaned up, and analyzed using the modified AOAC 991.31 and AOAC 2000.03 methods. All samples were ground with a blender. Each ground and spiked sample (25 g) was extracted with 125 mL methanol (75%). After blending vigorously for 30 min, the extract was filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper. For AF analysis, 15 mL filtrate was diluted with 30 mL distilled water and 15 mL of the supernatant was passed through an immunoaffinity column without preconditioning. For OTA analysis, 5 mL of the filtrate was diluted with 40 mL distilled water and 45 mL of the supernatant was passed through an immunoaffinity column without preconditioning. After the sample passed, the column was washed with 10 mL distilled water. Then, the column was air-dried and AFs were eluted with 1 mL methanol and OTA eluted with

1.5 mL of methanol–acetic acid (98 + 2, v/v). Finally, 1 mL and 1.5 mL distilled water were added for AFs and OTA, respectively, into a glass vial, and 100 µL of these eluates was directly injected for HPLC.

17.2 Analysis

Acetonitrile–methanol–water for AFs, and methanol–water–acetic acid for OTA were used as mobile phases to equilibrate RP HPLC columns before analyses. The wavelengths of excitation and emission were 365 and 435 nm for AFs, and 333 and 460 nm for OTA, respectively. The injection volume was 100 µL, and flow rate was 1.00 mL/min. Separation was achieved at 30°C under isocratic elution with the following mobile phases: acetonitrile–methanol–water (8 + 38 + 54, v/v/v) with 0.2 g/L potassium bromide, acidified with nitric acid (300 µL/L, 65%) for AF analysis and methanol–water–acetic acid (68.5 + 29 + 2.5, v/v/v) for OTA analysis.

18. Control procedures

A cereal sample not contaminated with mycotoxins was used as a blank sample for spiking.

Analyses of replicate spiked samples provided applicability and verification of the method.

19. Calculations and data analysis

The calculated and expected concentrations (C) of the spiked sample were compared to determine the recovery values using following equation:

$$\text{Recovery, \%} = [C_{\text{spiked sample}}/C_{\text{expected}}] \times 100$$

Results are expressed in µg kg⁻¹.

20. References

49.2.18 AOAC Official Method 991.31 Aflatoxins in Corn, Raw Peanuts, and Peanut Butter: Immunoaffinity Column (Aflatest) Method, <https://doi.org/10.1093/9780197610145.003.3973>

49.6.04 AOAC Official Method 2000.03 Ochratoxin A in Barley: Immunoaffinity Column HPLC, <https://doi.org/10.1093/9780197610145.003.4008>

Gazioğlu, I., & Kolak, U. (2015). Method validation for the quantitative analysis of aflatoxins (B1, B2, G1, and G2) and ochratoxin A in processed cereal-based foods by HPLC with fluorescence detection. *Journal of AOAC International*, 98(4), 939-945.

2.7. NARO

2.7.1. Dried products: dried fish (prototype n. 15a), fish powder (prototype n. 16)

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address:

Margaret Masette, mmasette@gmail.com; Samuel Edgar Tinyiro, tinyiro@gmail.com; Davis Akullo; Fred Wanda; and Aruho Cassius, aruhoc@gmail.com

2. Purpose

All collected samples were subjected to macro-nutrient analysis using standard AOAC methods.

3. Principle

Kjeldahl method (AOAC 1991); crude fibre Van Soest et al (1991); gross energy Harris, (1970); fat or lipid (AOAC 1990).

4. Definitions and abbreviations principles

N/A

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

Live fish, Nile tilapia, African Catfish, Labeo and Barbus sp. purchased from fish farmers. Stainless steel bins, knives, Ice, water, Solar tent, drying rack, waxed boxes. Carcasses, oven, hammer mill

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

N/A

5.2. Equipment, instruments

N/A

5.3. Health and Safety and personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

Overalls, boots, head covers, face masks, gloves, lab coats

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

An incision was made at the back of the head of the fish to allow for bleeding. Bleeding was done in a white container with water. After bleeding, the fish were thoroughly washed, split open in a butterfly way, guts removed and then washed again to remove all the bloodstains and any other form of dirt. In addition, for Tilapia, Labeo and Barbus sp., scales were removed. Samples for analysis were prepared in triplicate.

6.2. Analysis

Kjeldahl method (AOAC 1991) was used to quantify protein; Van Soest et al (1991) method was used to determine crude fibre while Harris, (1970) method was used determine gross energy and fat or lipid was determined by soxhlet system of extraction (AOAC 1990).

6.3. Schematic of method

N/A

6.4. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

N/A

7. Control procedures

Samples for analysis were prepared in triplicate.

8. Calculations and data analysis

Data were analysed using the statistical analysis system software package (Version 8.1, 2000; SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC, USA). One-way ANOVA was used to compare data sets with Duncan's multiple range test used to separate means ($p < 0.05$).

9. References

-AOAC (Association of Official Analytical Chemists) (1991). Official Methods of Analysis 15th Edition). AOAC Inc., Arlington, VA. 22201 USA

2.7.2. Oils from novel local varieties/species: fish oil (prototype n. 18)

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address:

Aruho Cassius, aruhoc@gmail.com; Wanda Fred; and Tinyiro Samuel, tinyiro@gmail.com

2. Purpose

Extraction of oil made from *Barbus altianalis*

3. Principle

Barbus altianalis is a fatty fish whose fat is largely characterised by omega 6 oils which are nutritionally important for human health. Normally when capture from the farm of wild the internal organs including the visceral fat are disposed of. However, it is important to ensure the fat is extracted for use in human consumption and avoid unnecessary disposal into the environment leading to pollution and waste.

4. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

Food grade boilers, thermometers, gloves, beakers, conical flasks, stands for distillation, food grade cooling pans, litmus paper, filter papers, parking bottles, Lipase protein enzyme, fat from visceral, Potable water, lfor activating the bentonite for purification of the liquid oil, Lab coats, nose masks, lab gaggles, gum puts, heavy duty hand gloves.

5. Procedures

Fish fat was obtained from freshly caught fish from the fish farm in Jinja, washed and sorted order to have only pure fat. The fat was then placed in ice box containers loaded with ice then transported to Aquaculture Research and Development Centre in Kajjansi. The fat temperature was measured and its weight determine as preliminary requirement for fish oil processing. The fish fat was again washed and the water discarded

6. Primary oil extraction

The fat was placed in the water bath and boiled to 80° C, there is separation of oil and water as the oil floats on the surface which is decanted off into food grade cooling containers. The fat

7. Secondary oil extraction

Upon cooling, preliminary filtration of the oil is than to remove tissue particles

- a. The oil (liquid + solid parts) are then treated with an activated Lipase enzyme that break down the bonds of the solid oils making it a liquid
- b. The oils are further treated in a water bath that will further break up any bonds still holding and let to cool in a covered environment
- c. The oils and waters are then separated by decantation

Treatment with Bentonite

- I. The oils are then heated to 89°C for a period of ten minutes
- II. The oils are then passed through a column packed with activated Bentonite and harvested from the lower end.
- III. The oils are then allowed to cool in a covered environment to 25°C
- IV. The oils are then packed in airtight bottles.

8. Calculations and data analysis

N/A

9. Reference

Unpublished report Nile perch report - NaFIRRI (2022).

2.7.3. Snacks from novel local varieties/species: fish cakes and crackers (prototype n. 22)

2.7.4. Other products from novel local varieties/species: other fish products (prototype n. 25a)

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address:

Margaret Masette, mmasette@gmail.com; Samuel Edgar Tinyiro, tinyiro@gmail.com; Davis Akullo; Fred Wanda; and Aruho Cassius, aruhoc@gmail.com

2. Purpose

Sensory evaluation of fish products

3. Principle

Fish and fishery products represent valuable sources of nutrients and contribute to diversified and healthy diets (FAO, 2013). Fish meat is a source of high biological value proteins, polyunsaturated fatty acids, vitamins and minerals, with the minerals mainly concentrated in the bones (Kabahenda *et al.*, 2011). The recognition of fish as a healthy meat by health-conscious consumers has led to the development of convenient fish products such as fish sausages, fish balls, fish burgers, as a way, not only to promote consumption but also add value to fish products for more earning by the traders. There is increased demand for affordable fish products so as to optimize the nutritional benefits by many consumers in the country. Fish products may not be affordable by many

communities especially the low-income earners, yet they need the fish to access some of the best protein sources and other nutrients from fish. Fish products such as balls, samosas, sausages among others could be affordable when they are processed in affordable quantities by many consumers. In addition, there are more byproducts we can get from the fish some of which may include the fish bones. Some of these products can be fortified with other products or food types and become cheaper and accessible by many consumers. Good processing of fish products can benefit both the consumers and the fish farmers. Fish farmers will earn more money from the value-added products and on one hand consumers will get what is affordable for them. Research has to continuously develop quality good products for consumers.

Sensory evaluation was done to determine the acceptability of the fish-based products. Sensory evaluation of the fish-based products was carried out according to Santana et al. (2015) by 30 trained panelists from Food Biosciences and Agribusiness Centre (NARL). After served in disposable cups. The panelists evaluated the samples using a 9-point hedonic scale where 1 denoted dislike extremely and 9 denoted like extremely. Sensory attributes evaluated included appearance, aroma, taste, texture and overall acceptability.

4. Definitions and abbreviations principles

N/A

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

Live fish Nile tilapia, African catfish were purchased from fish farmers in Kakiri, central Uganda, and Kampala city. The fish was transported to the food processing plant, National Agricultural Research Laboratories, Kawanda. The purchased fish material was kept in a freezer (-10°C) overnight. Other non-fish ingredients were purchased from local supermarkets around Kampala city. The fish materials were washed, gutted and washed, deboned, filleted, and then fillets and bones were washed under running tap until they were clean. The fish flesh was grinded using an electric grinder and the mince used in the preparation of fish balls, fish nuggets and fish crackers the bones dried for use in the preparation of extruded snacks.

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

N/A

5.2. Equipment, instruments

N/A

5.3. Health and Safety and personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

Overalls, boots, head covers, face masks, gloves, lab coats.

6. Procedures

Preparation of the secondary products.

6.1. Fish balls

The fish balls were prepared according to Duman and Peksezer (2016). Fish balls were composed of 64% fish meat and 36% other ingredients, including: 18% wheat flour, 11.4% onions, 1.8% bread crumbs, 3.8% fat, 0.7% salt and 0.26% black pepper. This basic mixture was processed to form small (25 g) balls and a deep-frying cooking method was applied. The fish balls were kept in a refrigerator for subsequent analysis.

6.2. Fish nuggets

The fish nuggets were prepared according to methods by Moosavi Nasab et al. (2018). The nuggets contained fish mince (80.24%), water (9.95%), lemon (0.30%), onion (6.01%), spices (0.36%), smoke powder (0.20%), phosphate (0.20%), wheat flour (1.50%) and dextrose (0.2). The nuggets were made into cylindrical shapes, coated with breadcrumbs, deep fried and kept in the refrigerator for subsequent analysis.

6.3. Fish crackers

The crackers were made following the method by Zzaman *et al.* (2017) with slight modification. They were made by mixing 200 g fish meat, 180 g tapioca starch, 12 g sugar, 13.5 g salt, 30.5 g ice, 3 g MSG, and 2.1 g sodium bicarbonate. The dough was shaped into cylindrical with 4.3 cm diameter and steamed at 90°C followed by chilling in refrigerator. It was cut into 2 mm thickness and put into oven of 50°C for 10 to 12 hours until the moisture content reading was 10% ± 2% and fried in vegetable oil.

6.4. Extruded fish bone-maize snack

Fish powder was prepared from the bones of tilapia and catfish. Maize was procured from specialty market and ground to pass through 200 µ sieve using laboratory mill. Several preliminary trials were made to select the proportion of fish flour incorporation in maize flour. The maize flour was mixed with the fish flour in the proportion of the fish bone flour was mixed with the maize flour in the ration of 1:2 in the ribbon blender for 15 min to ensure uniform mixing. Salt and other spices were added at 2% into the mix and again blended for 10 min (Shaviklo et al., 2011).

7. Calculation and data analysis

For proximate composition analysis, upon receiving the packed samples, dry sample were ground to powder while sub-dried samples were blended to homogeneity. Duplicate samples were obtained from each product and analysed in triplicate for crude protein, crude fat, dry matter and ash content. The crude protein was determined by Kjeldahl method while the crude oil was determined by Soxhlet method. Dry matter and ash were determined using forced air oven and muffle furnace respectively, (Laboratory SOPs for Nutrition analysis – ARDC Kajjansi).

8. References

-FAO and Smart Fish. (2013). *Fish consumption survey*. 1–88.

-Kabahenda, M. K., Amega, R., Okalany, E., & Heck, S. (2011). Protein and Micronutrient Composition of Low-Value Fish Products Commonly Marketed in the Lake Victoria Region. *World Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 7(5), 521–526.

2.8. ENAM

2.8.1. Oils from novel local varieties/species: virgin and/or extra virgin olive oil (prototype n. 17)

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address

Pr. Aadil Bajoub, ENAM, abajoub@enameknes.ac.ma

2. Purpose

The overall objective of the analyses carried out is to evaluate the quality of olive oil and to find the best technological solutions to produce high quality, stable and marketable olive oil products. The analysis carried out were: content of free fatty acids; peroxide value; specific extinction coefficients; content of fatty acids alkyl esters; PPPs content; 1,2-DAGs and sensory quality.

3. Principle

Over the last decades, olive oil quality and authenticity are subjects of current relevance because of increasing consumers' expectations (consumers have become very demanding about quality and show willingness to pay more for olive oils of outstanding quality), governmental regulations and the expanding competitiveness in the olive oil market. Indeed, the worldwide popularity gained by olive oil as a natural nutritious food (with specific chemical composition and sensory characteristics, with nutritional and healthy significance) has contributed to increase the consumption of this product, and, at the same time, to expand its production and consumption outside of the traditional Mediterranean producing countries. This has led to the existence of innumerable olive oil brands in the olive oil market, showing different quality grades and composition properties. Accordingly, the olive oil markets require, nowadays, greater transparency in the supply chain. Moreover, the assessment of quality and authenticity of the commercialized olive oils is becoming more and more important from the perspective of both the olive oil manufacturers and customers.

As any other food product, defining the overall concept of olive oil quality is a very difficult task, since there are different ways to address this subject. So, there is probably no single universal definition that adequately satisfies and covers all possible situations. However, olive oil quality can be described by (but not limited to) physicochemical and sensory quality indices (regulatory commercial quality), and nutritional value. Besides these intrinsic characteristics of the olive oil, the quality of this product can be established from a geographical and/or varietal perspective,

linking olive oil distinctive characteristics to a specific geographical area (concept of geographical indication systems) or to the use of a single olive variety (concept of monovarietal olive oils).

Regulated quality and the standards set by the IOC, the European Commission (EC), the *Codex Alimentarius* (Codex) and other regulatory systems are the binding way to define the quality of olive oil.

Briefly, in these regulations, a distinction among the different commercial grades of olive oil (extra virgin olive oil (EVOO), virgin olive oil (VOO), lampante virgin olive oil (LVOO) and ordinary virgin olive oil (considered only by IOC and *Codex Alimentarius* regulations)) is made on the basis of well-defined quality parameters: **the content of free fatty acids (FFAs)** (which measures the percentage of FFAs in the oil, expressed as % oleic acid); **the peroxide value (PV)** (which allows evaluating the state of primary oil oxidation (expressed in milliequivalents of active oxygen by kg of oil, meq O₂/kg)); and **the ultraviolet specific extinction coefficients**, conventionally indicated as K₂₃₂, K₂₇₀ and ΔK (that inform about the secondary oil oxidation state, and are measured in the UV region, at the wavelengths corresponding to the maximum absorption (about 232 and 270 nm) of secondary products formed in the autoxidation process). It should be noted, however, that in addition to these olive oil quality parameters adopted by all regulatory systems, there are other quality indices of no mandatory application, since no common decision has been made by consensus by all standardizing bodies. They involve **pyropheophytins (PPPs)** and **1,2-diacylglycerol (1,2-DAG)**, as indicators of olive oil freshness and the content on **fatty acid alkyl esters (FAAEs)**, which can be considered as indicator of the health conditions of processed olive fruits.

Besides these physico-chemical parameters, olive oil regulatory commercial quality definition includes the determination of its organoleptic characteristics. Within this frame, a methodology for evaluating the sensory attributes of olive oil, known as the “Panel Test method”, was developed in the ’80s by the IOC and later adopted by the EC (Regulation No. 640/2008) (EC, 2008) and other standardizing bodies. This methodology, also known as the IOC test, aims to identify and evaluate the intensities of positive and negative sensory perceptions for the classification of various grades of the tested olive oil. To do so, the IOC method defines the main steps for the selection and training of tasters, the minimum number of tasters to be involved in the sensory analysis, basic olive oil vocabulary (including both negative attributes, such as fusty/muddy, musty-humid-earthy, winey-vinegary-acid-sour and rancid; and positive attributes, mainly fruity, bitter and pungent), the tasting methodology to be followed, profile sheet and characteristics and specificity of tasting glass and booth (Figure 2.8.1.1).

Figure 2.8.1.1. Tasting glass and booths of the test room for olive oil sensory analysis.

4. Method of analysis

-Content of free fatty acids (FFAs).

Free fatty acids are the result of the hydrolytic degradation of triacylglycerols (TAGs), which can occur during the olive oil manufacturing process and storage. This degradation is caused by enzymes (lipases) naturally present in the olive fruit or by enzymes produced by micro-organisms growing on the fruit (De Oliveira et al., 2010). Olive oils produced from healthy fruits, irrespective of the cultivar, and processed immediately after harvesting typically exhibit very low FFAs content.

The official method for determining FFAs content, as established by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO 660 (ISO, 2009a)) and the American Oil Chemists Society (AOCS Cd 3d-63 (AOCS, 1999)), involves acid/base titration using potassium hydroxide with phenolphthalein as an indicator. The results are reported as a percentage (%) of oleic acid.

All regulatory bodies for olive oil set an upper limit for FFAs content to distinguish between commercial categories of olive oil. For virgin olive oils, the Californian regulation specifies lower limits for FFAs content to define the different grades within this category. While the IOC, EC, Codex, United States Department of Agriculture (USDA), and Australian standards set the upper limits at 0.8% for extra virgin olive oil (EVOO) and 2.0% for virgin olive oil (VOO), the Californian regulation sets these limits at 0.5% and 1.0%, respectively.

There are notable differences in how virgin olive oils with higher FFAs content are classified. EC, USDA, and Australian standards classify virgin olive oils with FFAs content exceeding 2.0% as lampante virgin olive oil (LVOO). In contrast, the Californian regulation considers oils with FFAs content over 1.0% as LVOO. The IOC regulation sets a higher upper limit, classifying virgin olive oil with FFAs content above 3.3% as LVOO. Both IOC and Codex standards are unique in setting this limit at 3.3%, meaning oils with FFAs values below or equal to this threshold are considered ordinary virgin olive oil (OVOO).

- Peroxide value (PV).

PV is an indicator of the primary oxidation status of olive oil, determined by measuring the concentration of hydroperoxides. These are the initial compounds formed during the degradation

of unsaturated fatty acids in olive oil. Hydroperoxides are not stable; their levels increase, reach a peak, and then decline due to further degradation into secondary oxidation products, such as ketones, aldehydes, and conjugated dienes (Mariotti, 2014).

The official method for determining PV, as specified by ISO 3960 (ISO, 2007) and AOCS Cd 8b-90 (AOCS, 2003), involves iodometric titration. This method measures the iodine released from potassium iodide when it reacts with the peroxides in the oil samples. Results are expressed as milliequivalents of active oxygen per kilogram of olive oil (meq O₂/kg oil).

Figure 2.8.1.3. Determination of the degree of oxidation of unsaturated fatty acids in olive oil expressed in meq O₂/Kg of olive oil.

Generally, the upper limit for PV used to grade olive oil is consistent across all standard legislations reviewed in this study. However, the Californian legislation sets a stricter upper limit for extra virgin olive oil (EVOO) at 15 meq O₂/kg, compared to 20 meq O₂/kg allowed by other regulations. Additionally, both Australian and Californian regulations establish a PV limit for lampante virgin olive oil (LVOO) at 20 meq O₂/kg, a parameter not considered in other regulatory standards.

- Ultraviolet specific extinction coefficients.

Conventionally indicated by K_{232} and K_{272} and obtained by the spectrophotometric measurements, in the ultraviolet, of extinctions of the olive oil sample diluted in cyclohexane at the wavelengths corresponding to the maximum absorption of the conjugated dienes and trienes, respectively, at about 232 and 270 nm (ISO 3656 (ISO, 2011) or AOCS Ch 5-91 (AOCS, 1991)). Besides, the absorption around 270 nm could also be caused by substances formed during earth treatment in the refining process. In addition to these parameters, ΔK value is often calculated according to the following equation: $\Delta K = K_{max} - [1/2(K_{max+4} + K_{max-4})]$ where K_{max} is the specific extinction at the wavelength for maximum absorption at 270 nm. Some differences among the considered regulatory systems can be found. Thus, for EVOO, the maximum permitted values of K_{232} , K_{270} (2.5 and 0.22, respectively) and ΔK ($\leq 1/0.01$) are the same for all the legislative standards. Likewise, when the VOO category is considered, all the

considered legislative standards require the same threshold values of K_{232} , K_{270} (2.6 and 0.25, respectively) and ΔK ($\leq /0.01$).

Figure 2.8.1.4. Measurement of K_{232} and K_{270} coefficients by ultraviolet spectrophotometry

- Content of fatty acid alkyl esters (FAAEs).

This quality criterion has been recently adopted by IOC and EU for the assessment of EVOO quality. However, so far, it is not considered by the other olive oil regulatory standards. FAAE compounds result from the esterification of FFAs with low molecular weight alcohols (mainly methanol and ethanol) yielding methyl and ethyl esters (Pérez-Camino et al., 2002; Boggia et al., 2014). The olive oil content in terms of these compounds was related to the health conditions of processed olive fruits. Indeed, damaged olive fruits were reported to be susceptible to undergo a hydrolytic process (lipolysis of TAGs with liberation of FFAs) and fermentative degradations (pectin demethylation and sugar fermentation), which create appropriate conditions for the synthesis of FAAEs (Biedermann et al., 2008). Furthermore, olive fruits storage before processing was reported to be a factor that increases the formation of these compounds. Other factors, such as inappropriate practices during oil extraction, catalyze the esterification reaction which increases the amount of these compounds in the obtained oils. In addition to their role as a quality parameter, FAAEs content has been reported as a relevant tool for detecting EVOO adulteration with low quality virgin olive oils, that have undergone a mild deodorization treatment conducted at a moderate temperature (≤ 100 °C), which remove volatile compounds that are responsible for their undesirable sensory attributes (Pérez-Camino et al., 2008). With regard to the analytical determination of FAAEs, the official method (COI/T.20/Doc. No 28 (IOC, 2010)) requires a preliminary separation of these compounds from the oil by means of a classical column chromatography, using silica gel as adsorbent, with hexane and ethyl ether as eluents; then, the solvents are evaporated by a rotary evaporator, and finally, the fraction containing the methyl and ethyl esters is diluted with n-heptane or iso-octane and analyzed by a GC system

for further identification and quantification purposes. IOC and EU regulate both the content of fatty acid methyl esters (FAMES) and fatty acid ethyl esters (FAEEs). A legal limit of 75 mg/kg for the sum of FAME and FAEE, or superior to 75 mg/kg and inferior to or equal to 150 mg/kg for the sum of FAME and FAEE (if the ratio of FAEE/FAME is below 1.5) was fixed for oils produced over the crop season 2012/2013 (EU Commission Regulation No 61/2011). However, from the crop season of 2013/2014, only FAEE content is considered, with a maximum value of 40, 35 and 30 mg/kg for oils produced during 2013/2014, 2014/2015 and 2015/2016, respectively (EU Commission Implementing Regulation No 1348/2013). After the crop season of 2016 the maximum value of FAEEs for the EVOO grade is going to be lower than 30 mg/kg (EU Commission Delegated Regulation 2015/1830).

- Content of pyropheophytins (PPPs):

Determination of PPPs content is only required by Australian and Californian standards for EVOO freshness evaluation. PPPs are formed during olive oil extraction and storage, due to the degradation of chlorophyll pigments (pheophytinization and a certain degree of allomerization). Chlorophyll breaks down to pheophytin a, then converts to pyropheophytins a as a result of the loss of the carbomethoxy group at carbon 13 (C13) (Aparicio-Ruiz et al., 2010; Guillaume et al., 2014). The generated amount of pyropheophytins a remains small, but their content in olive oil increases during the storage depending on various factors, such as olive fruits variety, ripeness and seasonal conditions (Gallardo-Guerrero et al., 2005). For this reason, the PPPs a content in terms of the ratio of pyropheophytin a divided by total pheophytins a -which is independent of these factors (Aparicio et al., 2013b)- was considered as a freshness parameter of EVOO. The standard method for the determination of PPPs content in olive oil (ISO 29841 (ISO, 2009b)) involves their separation using a miniaturized column chromatography on silica gel and chromatographic analysis using a reverse phase liquid chromatography with a photometric or fluorescence detector.

- 1,2-diacylglycerols (1,2-DAGs).

This is a quality and freshness parameter just considered by Australian and Californian standards for grading olive oil as EVOO. The estimation of this parameter is made by calculating the mass fraction ratio between 1,2-DAG and the sum of 1,2-DAGs and 1,3-DAGs. DAGs are present in virgin olive oils in low amounts (between 1% and 3%) as intermediate products of the biosynthesis of TAGs (1,2-DAGs) or as products of enzymatic or chemical hydrolysis of TAGs (1,3-DAGs) (Pérez-Camino et al., 2001). During storage, the 1,2-DAGs undergo isomerization, yielding 1,3-DAG, that are thermodynamically more stable. Consequently, assessing the amounts of these isomeric forms could be informative about the age and the freshness of virgin olive oils. Currently, the official method for the determination of this quality criterion (ISO 29822 (ISO, 2009c)) includes the separation of these isomeric forms on a silica gel chromatography

column, derivatization (silylation) and GC analysis. To classify a virgin olive oil as an EVOO, both Australian and Californian standards have set as minimum level the value of 35% for the ratio between 1,2-DAG and the sum of 1,2-DAG and 1,3-DAG (Table 2.8.1.1).

- Sensory quality.

Pleasant sensory characteristics of olive oil are one of the main reasons for the acceptability and preference of consumers of this foodstuff. In addition, the cultivation of various olive tree varieties in different pedoclimatic conditions and the use of diverse agronomical and technological techniques for olive extraction and production are the main factors behind the existence, in the olive oil market, of a myriad of olive oils with very distinctive flavour characteristics. The official method for the sensory evaluation of olive oil (COI/T.20/Doc. No 15 (IOC, 2007)) consists on a panel test method applied by a fully selected and trained taste panel recognized by the regulatory body. The method determines the category of olive oil according to the detection and intensity of sensory positive and negative attributes in the analyzed oil. Fruitiness, bitterness and pungency are sensory positive attributes determined by the panelists; whereas fusty-muddy, mustiness-humidity, winey-vinegary, frostbitten olives and rancid constitute the main defects. The panelists provide an intensity scale of each attribute, and then the MeF and MeD are calculated. Finally, each grade of olive oil is defined according to the obtained results. Thus, when no negative attributes are detected, and the MeF is superior to zero, all the regulatory standards classify the virgin olive oil as EVOO. However, some differences exist among these regulatory systems regarding the sensory evaluation of the other categories. Indeed, in the case of VOO grade, IOC and EU standards fix a maximum value of MeD of 3.5; whereas the other standards trades demand lower values (lower than or equal to 2.5). USDA, Australian and Californian standards classify all olive oils with a MeD superior to 2.5 as LVOO (also, in the case of USDA regulation, an olive oil is classified as LVOO when MeD is less than or equal to 2.5 and the MeF is equal to 0). EU standards, however, consider a higher value (3.5) (or when MeD is less than or equal to 3.5 and the MeF is equal to 0), and the IOC standards threshold is much higher for the LVOO category (value of MeD superior to 6 is established). Both IOC and Codex are the only ones defining olive oils with MeD value between 3.5 and 6 (or when MeD is less than or equal to 3.5 and the MeF is equal to 0), and between 2.5 and 6 (or when MeD is less than or equal to 2.5 and the MeF is equal to 0), respectively, as OVOO. For the other categories, mainly ROO, OO, OPO, and ROPO, the Australian and Californian standards are the only ones which set a limit value of MeD (2.5) for defining these grades. However, for the COPO category, neither regulatory trade limits of MeD nor MeF have been established.

5. Control procedures

A single batch per concentration (0%, 1%, 1.5%, and 2%) was prepared, and two replicates were taken from each batch. To enhance both reproducibility and accuracy, each replicate was then analyzed in triplicate for the various quality parameters.

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2.9. NUT

2.9.1. Other products: bean sauce (prototype n. 25b)

EXTRUDED BEAN FLOUR

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address:

Dorothy Nakimbugwe, Nutreal Limited, dnakimbugwe@gmail.com / nutrealfoods@gmail.com

2. Purpose

To determine the effect of extrusion processing on the nutritional properties of the developed bean flour

3. Principle

Common beans are highly nutritious, but the digestibility of the macronutrients and bioavailability of the micronutrients is limited by antinutritional factors such as trypsin inhibitors, lectins, polyphenols, and phytic acid, whose removal requires appropriate processing such as soaking, germination, and cooking (Ndagire et al., 2015; Nkudabombi et al., 2015) and extrusion cooking (Nattabirwa et al., 2017; Nattabirwa et al., 2018).

4. Definitions and abbreviations

N/A

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

N/A

5.2. Equipment, instruments

N/A

5.3. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

Laboratory coats, safety footwear, disposable gloves, protective eye goggles

Potential injury

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

Determination of nutritional properties of the extruded bean flour

Protein content of the sample was determined using the Kjeldahl method (AOAC 1990). In vitro protein digestibility was determined using pepsin-pancreatin enzyme system (Ndagire et al, 2015; Akande et al., 2017) before and after digestion. Total phytate content was determined by the titrimetric method described by Sarkiyayi and Agar (2010); Akande et al. (2017). Iron and zinc contents were determined using the Savant atomic absorption spectrophotometer (GBC Scientific Equipment Pty Ltd., Dandenong, Victoria, Australia, Model: A.C.N 005472686) as described by Okalebo, Gathua, and & Woomer (2002) and Akande et al. (2017). Iron and zinc extractability were determined using a method by Duhan, Khetarpaul, and Bishnoi (2002) and Akande et al. (2017).

6.2. Schematic of method

N/A

6.3. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

N/A

7. Control procedures

Analytical determinations were carried out in triplicate.

8. Calculations and data analysis

Protein digestibility was calculated as: % in vitro protein digestibility = $(A-B)/A$ where A is % protein in the sample before digestion and B is % protein after enzyme digestion. Tannin contents were expressed as mg catechin equivalent/100 mL of the sample.

Analyses were done in triplicates. Descriptive statistics (means) were calculated using Microsoft Excel. Means of different treatments were compared by applying analysis of variance and Turkey's test using SPSS software.

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2.9.2. Other products: amaranth-enriched wheat (prototype n. 25c)

DESCRIPTION OF THE ANALYTICAL METHODS USED FOR THE CHARACTERIZATION OF CHAPATIS MADE WITH AMARANTH ENRICHED WHEAT FLOUR

1. Name of the person in charge, institution, e-mail address:

Dorothy Nakimbugwe, Nutreal Limited, dnakimbugwe@gmail.com

2. Purpose

To determine the sensory acceptability of flat breads (chapati) made with developed amaranth-wheat flours

3. Principle

Determining the sensory acceptability of novel food products is key to their adoption and sustainable use/consumption. Chapatis are a popular snack food widely consumed in Uganda and East Africa in general. They are currently made purely of mostly imported wheat, making them less sustainable. Enriching the wheat with grain amaranth flour improves the nutritional content of the products (Tibagonzeka et al., 2014) while also making their consumption more sustainable.

4. Definitions and abbreviations principles

N/A

5. Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

5.1. Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

N/A

5.2. Equipment, instruments

Food ingredients: amaranth wheat flour; heat source and cooking utensils, condiments and spices, disposable plates and forks, paper serviettes, sensory ballots and pens

5.3. Health and Safety and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

Face masks, disposable gloves, sanitiser, overcoats, head covers and aprons

Potential food contamination

6. Procedures

6.1. Sample preparation

Chapatis were made using the 4 developed variants of amaranth-wheat flour, following a common recipe and procedure. Sensory evaluation of chapattis was performed by 40 (27 males and 13 females) semi-trained panelists from the Department of Food Technology and Nutrition at Makerere University. A 9 point hedonic scale was used to determine acceptability scores of sensory attributes of the chapatti samples where 1=dislike extremely, 2=dislike very much, 3=dislike moderately, 4=dislike slightly, 5=neither like nor dislike, 6=like slightly, 7=like moderately, 8=like very much and 9=Like extremely. Sensory data was analyzed using SPSS at 0.05% level of significance. Sensory acceptability was done based on mean scores for appearance, colour, and aroma, ease of rolling, texture, taste, aftertaste, mouth feel, and overall acceptability of the chapatis.

6.2. Analysis

The panelists evaluated the chapatis, in a sensory laboratory and recorded the responses on the ballot papers.

6.3. Schematic of method

N/A

6.4. Instrumentation: analytical conditions

N/A

7. Control procedures

N/A

8. Calculations and data analysis

Data for sensory attributes was analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Scientists 16.0 software program (SPSS software, release 16.0, SPSS Inc.). Means, standard deviations were determined, analysis of variance was performed to calculate significant differences ($P < 0.05$).

Sensory acceptability of chapatis made with the developed amaranth-wheat flours, on a 9-point hedonic scale

9. References

N/A

3. Determination of Acrylamide in Food Products

3.1 Purpose

Evaluate the content of acrylamide in cereal based products

3.2 Principle

Acrylamide is extracted and purified by SPE and then analysed by LC-ESI-MS/MS in positive ion mode (ESI⁺).

3.3 Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

- *Internal standard solution (¹³C₃-labelled acrylamide in MeOH)*
- *0.1% (v/v) formic acid*
- *Methanol (99.5/0.5, v/v)*
- *Stock solution of acrylamide with water in the 1.5–200 µg/L range*

Equipment, instruments

- *Agilent 6420 triple quadrupole (Agilent, Santa Clara, United States)*
- *Agilent 1290 Infinity LC Pump equipped with an autosampler and a thermostated column oven*

Health and Safety and personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

Acrylamide is a known carcinogen and genotoxicant, meaning it can damage DNA and potentially lead to cancer. Proper measures need to be undertaken when managing the analytical standard.

3.4 Procedures

Sample preparation

Food samples were finely ground before the extraction.

Analysis

1 g of sample was weighted into a polypropylene conical tube, and 100 μL 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ internal standard solution ($^{13}\text{C}_3$ -labelled acrylamide in MeOH) followed by 10 mL 0.1% (v/v) formic acid were added. After mixing with Vortex for 10 min, the extract was centrifuged at 4500 rpm for 15 min. A 2 mL portion of clarified solution was removed, avoiding collection of top oil layer when present, and filtered through paper filter. A solid-phase extraction (SPE) was performed using C18 cartridges (1000 mg, 6 mL; Phenomenex). Cartridges were first conditioned with 5 mL methanol followed by 5 mL water; 1 mL of filtered sample was loaded and washed with 1 mL water. Elution was performed with 1 mL acetone. Acetone was removed under nitrogen flow and sample was dissolved in 1 mL 0.1% (v/v) formic acid before injection. SPE clean-up was performed on 3 extracts for each sample.

HPLC-ESI-MS/MS analysis. LC-ESI-MS/MS in positive ion mode (ESI+) analyses were performed by an Agilent 6420 triple quadrupole (Agilent, Santa Clara, United States) coupled to an Agilent 1290 Infinity LC Pump equipped with an autosampler and a thermostated column oven, according to Calbiani, Careri, Elviri, Mangia, and Zagnoni (2004) with some modifications. The analytical column was a Poroshell 120 C18, 3.0 \times 100 mm, 2.7 μm (Agilent, USA) maintained at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The elution was in isocratic mode using a mixture of 0.1% (v/v) aqueous formic acid and methanol (99.5/0.5, v/v) as mobile phase at a flow rate of 0.3 mL/min. The sample injection volume was 10 μL . Full-scan analyses were performed in the 40–100 Da mass range, acquiring the following transitions: extracted ion at m/z 55, due to the transition 72 > 55, and at m/z 58, due to the transition 75 > 58 were used for the quantitative analysis. A calibration curve was made for the quantification diluting stock solution of acrylamide with water in the 1.5–200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ range. For acquisition and processing data, the Agilent MassHunter Workstation software was used.

Control procedures

All analytical determinations need to be carried out in triplicate to enhance both reproducibility and accuracy.

Calculations and data analysis

A calibration curve was made for the quantification diluting stock solution of acrylamide with water in the 1.5–200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ range. For acquisition and processing data, the Agilent MassHunter Workstation software was used.

Results are expressed in mg kg^{-1} of dry weight.

References

Calbiani, F., Careri, M., Elviri, L., Mangia, A., & Zagnoni, I. (2004). Development and single-laboratory validation of a reversed-phase liquid chromatography-electrospray tandem mass spectrometry method for identification and determination of acrylamide in foods. *Journal of AOAC International*, 87(1), 107–115.

4. Determination of Mycotoxins in Cereal-Based Products

4.1 Purpose

Evaluate the content of mycotoxins (aflatoxins and ochratoxin A) in cereal-based products

4.2 Principle

Modified AOAC 991.31 and AOAC 2000.03 methods for the simultaneous determination of total aflatoxins (AFs), aflatoxin B₁, and ochratoxin A (OTA) in cereal-based foods by RP-HPLC coupled with fluorescence detection. The AOAC 991.31 and AOAC 2000.03 methods were modified by changing sample preparation steps in the simultaneous determination of AFs and OTA. The same extraction process was used for both AF and OTA analysis.

The method is described by Gazioğlu & Kolak (2015).

4.3 Materials, Apparatus and Equipment

Solutions, standards, reagents and reference materials

- *Analytical standards of total AFs (AFB₁, AFB₂, AFG₁, and AFG₂), OTA, R-Biopharm (Darmstadt, Germany)*
- *Potassium bromide (≥99 purity, 104907),*
- *HPLC grade acetonitrile (≥99.93%purity),*
- *HPLC grade methanol (≥99.9% purity), nitric acid (65% purity), and glacial*
- *acetic acid (100% purity)0.1% (v/v) formic acid*
- *Phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) prepared by dissolving PBS tablets (Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany) in distilled water*

Stock solutions that contained 1000 ng/mL total AFs (AFB₁, AFB₂, AFG₁, and AFG₂) and 1000 ng/mL OTA were prepared from the purchased AF and OTA certified standards. The working standard solutions were prepared by diluting these stock solutions with methanol or methanol–water (60 + 40, v/v) to achieve different concentrations of mycotoxin mixtures. The calibration curve ranged from 0.08 to 10.00 ng/mL for total AFs and from 0.125 to 10.00 ng/mL for OTA. All prepared solutions were stored at -4°C and kept at room temperature in the dark for 30 min before their use.

Equipment, instruments

- *Aflaprep and Ochraprep immunoaffinity Columns - R-Biopharm (Darmstadt, Germany)*

- Shimadzu LC-20AT liquid chromatographic system (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) equipped with a fluorescence detector (RF-20A), autosampler system (SIL-20A), pump (LC-20AT), and column oven (CTO-10AS) and controlled by Lab Solutions software
- RP C18 column Cronusil-S ODS2 (4.6 × 250 mm, 100 Å, and 5 µm particle size; Gloucester, UK)
- KOBRA Cell electrochemical postcolumn derivatization system (R-Biopharm)

Health and Safety and personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

AFs and OTA are toxic substances; therefore, were always manipulated in solution, avoiding the formation of dust and aerosols. Nitrile gloves were used for all procedures

4.4 Procedures

Sample preparation

For Blank wheat samples were spiked with a suitable amount of mycotoxins to achieve 6.0 and 8.0 µg/kg total AFs, and 3.0 and 8.0 µg/kg OTA. After 30 min at room temperature, the spiked samples were extracted, cleaned up, and analyzed using the modified AOAC 991.31 and AOAC 2000.03 methods. All samples were ground with a blender. Each ground and spiked sample (25 g) was extracted with 125 mL methanol (75%). After blending vigorously for 30 min, the extract was filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper. For AF analysis, 15 mL filtrate was diluted with 30 mL distilled water and 15 mL of the supernatant was passed through an immunoaffinity column without preconditioning. For OTA analysis, 5 mL of the filtrate was diluted with 40 mL distilled water and 45 mL of the supernatant was passed through an immunoaffinity column without preconditioning. After the sample passed, the column was washed with 10 mL distilled water. Then, the column was air-dried and AFs were eluted with 1 mL methanol and OTA eluted with 1.5 mL of methanol–acetic acid (98 + 2, v/v). Finally, 1 mL and 1.5 mL distilled water were added for AFs and OTA, respectively, into a glass vial, and 100 µL of these eluates was directly injected for HPLC.

Analysis

Acetonitrile–methanol–water for AFs, and methanol–water–acetic acid for OTA were used as mobile phases to equilibrate RP HPLC columns before analyses. The wavelengths of excitation and emission were 365 and 435 nm for AFs, and 333 and 460 nm for OTA, respectively. The injection volume was 100 µL, and flow rate was 1.00 mL/min. Separation was achieved at 30°C under isocratic elution with the following mobile phases: acetonitrile–methanol–water (8 + 38 + 54, v/v/v) with 0.2 g/L potassium bromide, acidified with nitric acid (300 µL/L, 65%) for AF analysis and methanol–water–acetic acid (68.5 + 29 + 2.5, v/v/v) for OTA analysis.

Control procedures

A cereal sample not contaminated with mycotoxins was used as a blank sample for spiking.

Analyses of replicate spiked samples provided applicability and verification of the method.

Calculations and data analysis

The calculated and expected concentrations (C) of the spiked sample were compared to determine the recovery values using following equation:

$$\text{Recovery, \%} = [C_{\text{spiked sample}}/C_{\text{expected}}] \times 100$$

Results are expressed in $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$.

References

49.2.18 AOAC Official Method 991.31 Aflatoxins in Corn, Raw Peanuts, and Peanut Butter: Immunoaffinity Column (Aflatest) Method, <https://doi.org/10.1093/9780197610145.003.3973>

49.6.04 AOAC Official Method 2000.03 Ochratoxin A in Barley: Immunoaffinity Column HPLC, <https://doi.org/10.1093/9780197610145.003.4008>

Gazioğlu, I., & Kolak, U. (2015). Method validation for the quantitative analysis of aflatoxins (B1, B2, G1, and G2) and ochratoxin A in processed cereal-based foods by HPLC with fluorescence detection. *Journal of AOAC International*, 98(4), 939-945.

